

Afrotropical Myzininae of the subtribe Meriina (with identification key for the genus *Meria* Illiger, 1807) (Hymenoptera: Tiphidae)

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Abstract. A key of all known species of the genus *Meria* Illiger, 1807 of the Afrotropical region is given. Eleven new species are described: *Meria aequatorialis* n. sp., *Meria conophora* n. sp., *Meria eterodira* n. sp., *Meria hermonensis* n. sp., *Meria mhaladai* n. sp., *Meria namibensis* n. sp., *Meria ordinaria* n. sp., *Meria ornativentris* n. sp., *Meria peripatetica* n. sp., *Meria shabeella* n. sp., *Meriodes laticeps* n. sp. Two taxa of the genus *Poecilotiphia* are described from Austral Africa for the first time: *Poecilotiphia australis* n. sp., *Poecilotiphia idioptera* n. sp. Lectotypes of *Plesia meruensis* Cameron, 1910, *Meira rufitarsis* Cameron, 1910, *Myzine (Hemimeria) sublevis* Turner, 1908, *Myzine (Pseudomeria) neavei* Turner, 1911, *Myzine umbratica* Turner, 1912, *Myzine impetuosus* Turner, 1913, *Myzine basatorum* Turner, 1913 are designed and their new combinations under *Meria* are established. The shift of *Meria anomala* Boni Bartalucci, 2009 to *Afromeria* Boni Bartalucci, 2007 is proposed besides the synonymy of *Mesa erythrodira* Boni Bartalucci, 2013 with *Elis (Mesa) arnoldi* Turner, 1917.

Riassunto. Myzininae afrotropicali della sottotribù Meriina (con chiave di identificazione del genere *Meria* Illiger, 1807) (Hymenoptera: Tiphidae). Viene fornita una nuova chiave di identificazione per le specie del genere *Meria* Illiger, 1807 della regione Afrotropicale e vengono descritte 11 nuove specie: *Meria aequatorialis* n. sp., *Meria conophora* n. sp., *Meria eterodira* n. sp., *Meria hermonensis* n. sp., *Meria mhaladai* n. sp., *Meria namibensis* n. sp., *Meria ordinaria* n. sp., *Meria ornativentris* n. sp., *Meria peripatetica* n. sp., *Meria shabeella* n. sp., *Meriodes laticeps* n. sp. Per la prima volta sono descritte due specie del genere *Poecilotiphia* dall' Africa australe: *Poecilotiphia australis* n. sp., *Poecilotiphia idioptera* n. sp. Vengono designati i lectotipi di *Plesia meruensis* Cameron, 1910, *Meira rufitarsis* Cameron, 1910, *Myzine (Hemimeria) sublevis* Turner, 1908, *Myzine (Pseudomeria) neavei* Turner, 1911, *Myzine umbratica* Turner, 1912, *Myzine impetuosus* Turner, 1913, *Myzine basatorum* Turner, 1913 e stabilita la loro nuova combinazione sotto il genere *Meria*. Viene proposto lo spostamento di *Meria anomala* Boni Bartalucci, 2009 nel genere *Afromeria* Boni Bartalucci, 2007 oltre alla sinonimia di *Mesa erythrodira* Boni Bartalucci, 2013 con *Elis (Mesa) arnoldi* Turner, 1917.

Key words. *Meria*, *Meriodes*, *Poecilotiphia*, new species, Afrotropical Region.

Introduction

The genus *Meria* is widely spread over warmer arid and semiarid countries of the Old World. About Afrotropical Region most of the taxa hitherto known come from Austral Africa also because South African areas have been by far the most investigated ones (CAMERON 1905; TURNER 1908, 1910, 1911, 1912, 1913, 1916, 1917, 1926; BINGHAM 1912; JACOT GUILLARMOD 1953, 1961; BONI BARTALUCCI 2001, 2004a, 2005, 2007, 2009).

Material and methods

The terminology used in the descriptions follows BONI BARTALUCCI (2004b).

Abbreviations

A = height (Alt itudo)	N₃ = meta Not um.
a = fore (an terioris)	O = eye (O culus)
CC = costal cell (<i>C</i> ella <i>C</i> ostal <i>s</i>)	oc = oc ellum
CD II = 2 nd discoidal cell (<i>C</i> ella <i>D</i> iscoidal <i>s</i> secunda)	p = puncture (-s), punctured
CHy = hypostomal keel (car ina H ypostomae)	P = Prop odeum
cOc (& co) = carina O ccipit <i>s</i> (-alis)	Pal = labial palpus (P alpus labialis)
CPM = paramarginal cell (<i>C</i> ella <i>P</i> ara <i>M</i> arginalis)	Pam = maxillary palpus (P alpus maxillar <i>s</i>)
CSM = sub marginal cell (<i>C</i> ella <i>S</i> ub <i>M</i> arginalis)	PoG = genal bridge (P ons G enarum)
Em₃ = meta E pimeron	Sc₁ = S cutum.
Es₁ = propleurae	Sc₂ = S cutellum.
Es₂ = meso E pisternum (mesopleurae)	Secu = S ensilla cur vata
FoO = oral cavity (F ossa O ris)	Ssa = Subantennal sclerite (Sclerit <i>s</i> sub antenna)
G = G ena	St₃ = meta S ternum
Hyp = H ypostoma	Ste = S ternum (a) of metamerus (i)
Hypc = H ypostomal carina	su₃ = metapleural line (sul cus metapleurae)
l = lateral (lateralis)	sul = lateral furrow (sul cus lateralis)
LA = width (L Atitudo)	supar = paramarginal furrows (sul cus paramarginalis)
LaSt₂ = mesosternal lobes (L amellae meso S terni)	Ter = T ergum (a) of metameri
m = median (med ianus)	To = T orulus
max = most (max imum)	Tsa = supra antennal lobes (T uberculi supra antenna)
mpm = paramandibular edge (m argo p ara m andibularis)	X = coxa
N₁ = pro N otum.	X₃ = hind coxa (co X a posterioris)

Those referred to the wing structures are in italics .

! = Types examined; () = digits between round brackets in the chorological items mean number of specimens; / / = delimit the single label. Within the descriptions of labels, italic characters mean handwriting.

The frontal aspect of the head is performed perpendicularly to the virtual plane A indicated by the relative line on the Fig. 1; dorsal and lateral aspects, perpendicular to each other, are performed along the virtual plane of the occipital carina. About the morphological terms the well established English words have been used, otherwise the latin form has been preferred. Some other specifications have to be stressed to avoid misunderstandings about the terminology; following GOULET & HUBER (1993) the term metasternum refers only to the mesosomal sclerite, while the ventral sclerites of the metasoma have to be simply named “sternum (-a)” and the relative dorsal sclerites “tergum (-a)”. “Metamerus (-i)” refers to every entire single segment of the metasoma. Postscutellum or postscutellar area here means the central area of metanotum (**N₃**) between the large lateral pits. The term “colpus” introduced by ARGAMAN (1994) means a gradulus with a more or less deep socket just under it along its length. Characters are listed giving priority to those shared both by females and males and at any case following the scheme: anterior→posterior, dorsal→ventral, basal→apical.

The outermost pair of appendages of male genitalia will be termed “gonosquama”. The drawings of the volsella and gonosquama show respectively their inner and outer lateral aspect, unless otherwise indicated. Aedeagus too shows its lateral aspect. Genitalia are settled in a solidified drop of 5,5-dimethyl hidantoin formaldehyd (5,5-DMHF) on a transparent support. Hair, punctuation and light markings have been overlooked in most of the drawings.

Acronyms

BMNH = Natural History Museum, London. CUIC = Cornell University Insect Collection, Ithaca. MSNP = Museo di Storia Naturale e del territorio dell’Università di Pisa, Calci (PI). MZUF = Museo di Storia Naturale dell’Università degli Studi di Firenze, sezione di Zoolgia “La Specola”, Firenze. NHRS = Naturhistoriska Riksmuseet, Stockholm. NMNW = National Museum of Namibia, Windhoek. NNIC = Namibian National Insect Collection. OLML = Oberösterreichische

Landesmuseum, Linz. RMNH = Museum of Natural History (Naturalis), Leiden. SAM = South African Museum, Capetown. USNM = United States National Museum, Washington.

Taxonomy

Mesa Saussure, 1892

Mesa arnoldi (Turner, 1917)

Elis (Mesa) arnoldi: TURNER (1917: 63). Holotypus, ♂: Zimbabwe = /Bulawayo III.1913 - Rhodesia Museum/ /*Elis (Mesa) arnoldi* Turn. *Type*/ /Type H.T./ (rounded with red outer ring) BMNH !

Mesa erythrodira: BONI BARTALUCCI (2013: 1694, Figs 194-197) **Nova Syn.**

The examination of the holotypes revealed their perfect identity, apart the minor size of Turner's specimen.

Meria Illiger, 1807

The previous key given in BONI BARTALUCCI (2009) has to be considered obsolete of course.

Identification key

Females

1

Males

28

1

- α** Genal bridge more than 0.8 times height of **FoO** in ventral aspect (Fig. 2)
- β** Glossa sub-triangular in ventral aspect, without any apical notch (Fig. 3)
- χ** The complex glossa-paraglossa strongly shorter than prementum (Fig. 3)
- δ** Posterior lingual plate not elongated (Fig. 3)
- ε** Labrum with a slightly concave ventral edge in frontal aspect (Fig. 4)
- φ** Scape: long bristles along its entire upper length (Fig. 5)

oinodes Boni Bartalucci, 2009

- αα** Genal bridge at most about 0.5 times height of **FoO** in ventral aspect (Fig. 6)
- ββ** Glossa distinctly notched apically (well detectable in ventral aspect; less stressed in *M. rufinodis* and *M. luteipes*) (Fig. 7)
- χχ** The complex glossa-paraglossa normally well longer than either in few cases just abit shorter than prementum (Fig. 7)
- δδ** Posterior lingual plate elongated with the main axis more than twice the minor axis (Fig. 7)
- εε** Labrum with a clearly convex and prominent ventral edge in frontal aspect (Fig. 8)
- φφ** Scape: long bristles along $\frac{3}{4}$ its entire upper length at most

2

2

- α** Clypeus with a stripe of multiple rows of densely packed small **p** bearing short bristles along most of its ventral border and base of the ventral lamella (Figs 13, 86); more often **p** extends medially up to the broad keel on the upper clypeus and laterally till to cover most of its surface
- β** **mpm** strongly turning towards clypeus before meeting **Hypc** (Fig. 9)
- χ** Inner lobe of mandible weakly prominent, its upper sub tooth either very feeble either not expressed (Figs 13, 86)
- δ** Ventral **Es₂** completely and regularly **p** without large smooth areas just next to **LaSt₂** which have a cluster near their apex and a stripe of **p** along their mutual inner edge (but in *M. limata*)

3

- αα** Most of clypeus smooth and shining, with only a single row of **p**, along the base of the lamella (Fig. 10), only in *M. rufinodis* and *M. luteipes* it resemble to state **α**
- ββ** **mpm** almost straight, only scarcely turning towards clypeus to meet **Hypc** (Fig. 11). *M. neavei* shows **β** state

χχ Inner lobe of mandible prominent, its upper sub tooth well expressed (Fig. 10), *M. luteipes* shows **χ** state
δδ Ventral **Es**₂ with large smooth areas next to **LaSt**₂ which is almost completely smooth, with only very few p at its apex at the most

11

3

α Median area of clypeus flat, without well detectable vertical prominence
β Base of hypostomal carina evenly rounded in ventral aspect (Fig. 9)
χ Upper sub tooth of the lobe on the inner edge of the mandible not expressed (very feeble in *M. discontinua*) (Fig. 86)
δ Propodeal disk with a well produced median furrow and lateral punctuation
ε Forewing with 2nd **CSM** present. Pterostigma with a well differentiated inner area (Figs 85, 87)
φ Coastal vein of hindwing without bristles along its edge basally to hamuli; only secondary hamuli eventually present
γ Hindtibial spurs with straight subparallel edges along most of their length (tapered at their base and apex)

4

αα Median area of clypeus convex with a well expressed low and blunt vertical prominence
ββ Base of hypostomal carina with a median small protuberance in ventral aspect (Fig. 12)
χχ Upper sub tooth of the lobe on the inner edge of the mandible just poorly expressed (Fig. 13)
δδ Propodeal disk without any furrows or with a very short one and mostly smooth surface
εε Forewing without 2nd **CSM**. No differentiated area within pterostigma
φφ Hindwing with a series of bristles as long as, or longer than, height of the **CC** along the edge of the c basally to hamuli
γγ Hindtibial spurs more or less enlarged on their apical third

(Group of *limata*) 7

4

α Upper sub tooth of the lobe on the inner edge of the mandible feebly expressed
β Body completely brown-dark brown without any ferruginous colloration
discontinua (Schultz, 1906)

αα Upper sub tooth of the lobe on the inner edge of the mandible not expressed
ββ Metasoma more or less extensively ferruginous

5

5

α Clypeal disk: ratio width/median height (including lamella) about 1.3 in frontal aspect
β Hypostomal area slightly swollen not breaking **cOe** which is complete ventrally
χ Ratio **LA/A** of the **N**₁ disk about 2 in dorsal aspect
δ Large area on postero ventral corner of lateral **N**₁ with large irregular wrinkles
phainoprocta Boni Bartalucci, 2009

αα Clypeal disk: ratio width/median height (including lamella) more than 2 in frontal aspect
ββ Hypostomal area strongly swollen and breaking **cOe** which is broadly interrupted ventrally
χχ Ratio **LA/A** of the **N**₁ disk about 2.4 in dorsal aspect
δδ Lateral **N**₁ without large irregular wrinkles anywhere

6

6

α Clypeal disk: ratio width/median height (including lamella) more than 2.8 in frontal aspect
β Upper surface of clypeal disk with large smooth areas
χ Cupreous hair on the whole body, lighter on metasoma
δ Metasoma completely ferruginous but reddish brown 1st sternal surface and shadings on 1st **Ter**, without any light patches
dissimilis Boni Bartalucci, 2009

αα Clypeal disk: ratio width/median height (including lamella) about 2.1 in frontal aspect (Fig. 86)
ββ Upper surface of clypeal disk completely **p** (Fig. 86)

χχ Yellowish hair on the whole body, but brown hair on the scape and frons
δδ Metasoma with lateral apical ivory patches on 2nd and 3rd **Ter**. Brown basal two metameri; dark ferruginous colour on 3rd to 6th metameri with brown shadings on lateral surfaces
noorti nova sp.

7

α Clypeal disk densely **p**, and haired throughout but small lateral areas
β N₁ and propodeal disk largely punctured
χ Forewing: dense series of bristles as long as thickness of **CC** along the edge of the **c** vein basally to pterostigma
δ Forewing: apical veins of **CPM** and **CD II** tubular even though less thick than all the other veins
ε Hind tibial spurs spatula-like with strongly enlarged apical third
φ Long bristles on the hindtarsomerus arranged in a well distinct row (as it happens in *Macromeria*)
γ Microreticulation on 6th tergum larger and more impressed, evident at x10 magnifications too
lasiotera Boni Bartalucci, 2009

αα Clypeal disk with large smooth and hairless areas
ββ N₁ and propodeal disk largely smooth
χχ Forewing without bristles along the edge of the **c** vein
δδ Apical veins of the forewings (**CPM** and **CD II**) nebulous
εε Hind tibial spur with only slightly enlarged apical third
φφ Scattered long bristles on the hindtarsomerus, not arranged in a well distinct rows
γγ Microreticulation on 6th tergum fine and well detectable only at about x30 magnifications

8

8

α Ventral **Es**₂ with large smooth area near **LaSt**₂
β **LaSt**₂ completely puncture-less
limata (Smith, 1855)

αα Ventral **Es**₂ with regularly packed **p** near **LaSt**₂, without any smooth area
ββ **LaSt**₂ with aevident clusters and stripes of **p** on **LaSt**₂

9

9

α Declivitous surface of N₁ between disk and collar smooth and shining
β Metasoma completely bright ferruginous, petiole included, nowhere brown shades
bonaespei (Turner, 1926)

αα Declivitous surface of N₁ between disk and collar completely covered by shallow **p**
ββ Metasoma not completely ferruginous; the petiole and more or less extended shades at least on the first metamerus are brown

10

10

α Vertex of head rounded and temples very narrow in frontal aspect
β Palpi straw-coloured
χ **Pam**: basal five elements almost isometric
δ N₁ disk completely ferruginous. Metasoma ferruginous either with brown shades on the first two-three metameri either with the basal three metameri completely brown
 (Fig. 21) *sublevis* (Turner, 1908)

αα Vertex of head subrectilinear and large temples in frontal surface
ββ Palpi brownish
χχ **Pam**: basal element just a bit less than twice longer than 4th and 5th elements
δδ N₁ disk black/dark brown. Metasoma ferruginous-brown with brown shades throughout
deiandra Boni Bartalucci, 2009

11

- α** Ventral lamella of clypeal disk: lateral corner raised up on its main plain in ventral aspect (Figs 11 & 12)
β Upper sub-tooth of the inner lobe of the mandible strongly bulging in frontal aspect (Fig. 12)
χ Labrum ventral surface: the waved row of **p** bearing long bristles strongly bent, its distance from posterior edge medially more than twice than laterally (Fig. 14)
δ More often than not medium to large species (the largest ones within the genus) from 11 to 21 mm. Only one taxon less than 10 mm

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- αα** Ventral lamella of clypeal disk without raising lateral corner in ventral aspect (like Fig. 9)
ββ Upper sub-tooth of the inner lobe of the mandible weakly bulging (but *M. perornata* and *M. pallidipes*)
χχ Labrum ventral surface: the waved row of **p** with long bristles holds throughout about the same distance from the posterior edge (Fig. 15)
δδ Small to medium sized up till 12 mm at most

19

12

- α** Mid suture of **PoG** expressed by a strong rib. **PoG** area with two crests at its sides originating from the hypostomal carina, converging to each other posteriorly and breaking **cOc** (Fig. 16)
β Strongly developed **N₁** in dorsal aspect, ratio **LA/A_m** about 1.4 (Fig. 17)
χ Exposed **Sc₁** very narrow, ratio **LA/A** more than 6. Parapsidal lines (**supar**) and notauli reduced to a single **p** (Fig. 17)
δ **Es₁** prominent, getting to a sort of mucrone
ε Forewing deeply bilobed, just a bit longer than mesosoma, with very reduced cells, like in *M. geniculata* (Brullé, 1832). Stigma situated before one/fifth from the base of the forewing. Wings shorter than aggregate length of head and mesosoma in dorsal aspect (Fig. 17)
φ 2nd dorsal **Ter** with a broad, white, transverse band (Fig. 17)

neavei (Turner, 1911)

- αα** Mid suture of **PoG**, where present, expressed at best only by a simple not prominent line
ββ **N₁** in dorsal aspect with a ratio **LA/A_m** more than 2
χχ Exposed **Sc₁** less narrow in dorsal aspect, ratio **LA/A** less than 4. **supar** and notauli expressed as furrows
δδ **Es₁** low and evenly rounded
εε Normal forewing like in *M. tripunctata*, with 2nd **CSM** too
φφ 2nd and 3rd **Ter** only with a lateral spot

13

13

- α** Very large lamella on the ventral clypeal border, as wide as ¾ its total width
β Propodeal disk strongly wrinkled and sculptured throughout, without any smooth area
cruenta (Turner, 1916)

- αα** Central lamella of the clypeus no longer than 3/5 its total width
ββ Propodeal disk with more or less extended smooth polished areas

14

14

- α** Dorsal area of propodeal disk almost completely smooth, without **p** and with weak lateral wrinkles; median furrow either absent either vestigial
namachorites Boni Bartalucci, 2009

- αα** Dorsal area of propodeal disk broadly **p** and more impressed wrinkles; median furrow long and well impressed

15

15

- α** Body mostly dark brown without ferruginous colour

16

αα Head and/or metasoma with more or less extensively light brown and/or ferruginous areas and shadings 17

16

α Head strongly transversal in frontal aspect. Ratio **LA/A** more than 1.5 (**A** = measured from the tip of vertex to the base of ventral lamella of clypeus, in frontal aspect)
β Body dark brown throughout
χ Brown bristles all over the body
δ Wings strongly darkened
ε Well expressed gradulus on 3rd **Ter**

(Fig. 22) *umbratica* (Turner, 1912)

αα Head less transversal in frontal aspect. Ratio **LA/A** no more than 1.4 (**A** = measured from the tip of vertex to the base of ventral lamella of clypeus)
ββ Body brown with large light brown areas
χχ Whitish bristles all over the body
δδ Wings only slightly infumated
εε Undetectable gradulus on 3rd **Ter**

rufitarsis (Cameron, 1910)

17

α Head always almost completely bright ferruginous and metasoma black or dark brown.
β Great size, up to 20 mm

rufifrons (Fabricius, 1793)

αα Head brown/dark brown, with ferruginous shadings at the most. Metasoma brown to ferruginous
ββ Variable size

18

18

α Head largely transversal in frontal aspect. Ratio **LA/A** about 1.5 (**A** = measured from the tip of vertex to the base of ventral lamella of clypeus)
β Row of strong black bristles along the whole width of clypeal disk
χ Head often with ferruginous areas. Mesosoma dark brown. Metasoma either completely ferruginous either more often than not with brown basal metameri
δ Great size, 12-18 mm

fusifformis (De Geer, 1778)

αα Head in frontal aspect with a Ratio **LA/A** about 1.2
ββ Clypeus largely smooth with a small tuft of weak whitish hair just in the middle above ventral lamella
χχ Head and mesosoma brown black, metasoma mostly ferruginous with brown shades on basal metamerus
δδ Small size (8-9 mm)

(Fig. 23) *basutorum* (Turner, 1913)

ααα Head in frontal aspect with a Ratio **LA/A** a bit less than 1.3
βββ Clypeus largely smooth with a row of whitish hair along the whole width of clypeal disk
χχχ Body brown to dark brown with lighter apical metameri
δδδ Medium size, 11-13 mm

erythraea Boni Bartalucci, 2009

19

α Apical stripe of **Tsa** thickened, with a gradulus dividing it from the remainder of surface (Fig. 18)
β Not prominent mid suture of **PoG** with contiguous area delimited by two lateral parallel ribs originating from the hypostomal carina and getting **cOc** (Fig. 19)

(Fig. 19) *perornata* (Turner, 1908)

αα Apical stripe of **Tsa** evenly rounded without any gradulus
ββ Mid suture of **PoG**, where expressed, like a simple not prominent line without any rib

20

20

- α** Strongly developed **N**₁ in dorsal aspect, ratio **LA/A**_m about 1.4 (Fig. 110)
β Exposed **Sc**₁ very narrow with ratio **LA/A** more than 6. **supar** very short, notauli reduced to a single **p** (Fig. 110)
χ Wings well shorter than length of the sole mesosoma, with reduced cells to less than one fourth of their total length (Figs 111, 112)

peripatetica nova sp.

- αα** **N**₁ in dorsal aspect with ratio **LA/A**_m more than 2
ββ Exposed **Sc**₁ less narrow with ratio **LA/A** less than 4. **supar** and notauli normally expressed by a groove
χχ Forewing like in *M. tripunctata*, often with 2nd **CSM** too

21

21

- α** Head strongly transversal in frontal aspect: ratio **LA/A** (**A** = from the middle point of **Tsa** to the edge of vertex a bit less than 1.6)
β 2nd tergum with gradulus greatly arched; ratio **LA/A**_m of postgradular surface in dorsal aspect about 4
χ Metasoma completely bright ferruginous, petiole included

diapyrogastra Boni Bartalucci, 2009

- αα** Head not so transversal in frontal aspect: ratio **LA/A** (**A** = from the middle point of **Tsa** to the edge of vertex) 1.4 at most
ββ 2nd tergum with gradulus almost rectilinear; ratio **LA/A**_m of postgradular surface in dorsal aspect about 3
χχ Metasoma with at least dark brown petiole and part of 1st tergum

22

22

- α** Lateral ocelli very near vertex in frontal aspect, their distance from vertex less than half their relative distance

23

- αα** Lateral ocelli more distanced from vertex in frontal aspect, the distance from vertex longer than half, up to twice, their relative distance

24

23

- α** Acute lateral corner of ventral lamella of clypeal disk in frontal aspect
β Mesosoma always wider than 2nd metamerus in dorsal aspect
χ Metasoma with white lateral spots on 2nd and 3rd terga at least

luteipes Boni Bartalucci, 2005

- αα** Rounded lateral corner of ventral lamella of clypeal disk in frontal aspect
ββ Mesosoma a bit less or at most as wide as 2nd metamerus in dorsal aspect
χχ Metasoma without any light patches

stenogastra Boni Bartalucci, 2009

24

- α** Hypostomal base slightly swollen not getting **cOc**, **PoG** well expressed

25

- αα** Hypostomal base swollen and getting **cOc**, **PoG** not expressed

26

25

- α** Distance **oc**_m/**oc**₁ more than twice shorter than both distance **oc**₁/**O** and distance **oc**_m from the edge of the vertex
β Forewing somewhat shortened: distance of apical tip of pterostigma from the edge of tegula less than half total length

- χ** Forewing with petiolated 2nd *CSM* *quadrata* (Turner, 1913)
- αα** Distance **oc_m/oc₁** only more than half both distance **oc₁/O** and distance **oc_m** from the edge of the vertex (Fig. 89)
- ββ** Forewing: distance of apical tip of pterostigma from the edge of tegula more than half total length (Fig. 88)
- χχ** Forewing without petiolated 2nd *CSM* (Fig. 88) *ordinaria* nova sp.

26

- α** Clypeal lamella narrow and very poorly protruding under the line connecting the ventral edges of lateral lobes in frontal aspect
- β** Propodeal disk with a deep median furrow and strongly wrinkled laterally and posteriorly; only smooth shining subtriangular areas along the mid furrow (Fig. 42) *pallidipes* (Turner, 1916)

- αα** Higher clypeal lamella well protruding under the line connecting the ventral edges of lateral lobes in frontal aspect
- ββ** Propodeal disk with larger, irregular smooth areas, less impressed median furrow and only poorly wrinkled at most 27

27

- α** Body basic colour brown with extended ferruginous red and white markings
- β** Metasoma with large white patches on 1st to 5th terga with two small ones on 2nd and 3rd sternum too.
- χ** Brown-black hair with cupreous reflections all over the body
- δ** Large size: 14 mm *multipicta* (Turner, 1913)
- αα** Black head and mesosoma; bright ferruginous metasoma but dark brown entire petiole and 1st sternum
- ββ** No white markings
- χχ** Whitish hair all over the body; brown hair only on the scape
- δδ** Medium size: 8-11 mm (Fig. 24) *rufinodis* (Turner, 1910)

28

- α** Glossa without a detectable notch apically (Fig. 25)
- β** Posterior lingual plate bluntly elliptic, with main axis far less than twice the minor one (Fig. 25)
- χ** Foretibia spur with velum narrower than trunk, with a waving edge and a short apical tooth; velum without defined combed edge (Fig. 26) *oinodes* Boni Bartalucci, 2009

- αα** Glossa notched apically (Well detectable in ventral aspect) less stressed in *M. rufinodis* (Fig. 27)
- ββ** Posterior lingual plate elongated with main axis more than twice the minor one (Fig. 27)
- χχ** Foretibial spur with velum larger than trunk, with a straight edge and longer prominent apical tooth; velum with a large combed edge (Fig. 28) 29

29

- α** N₁ with an elongated habitus in dorsal aspect. Its LA_a just a bit greater than A₁ (1.03 to 1.15) (Fig. 29)
- β** Metasternum (St₃) stout, without prominent sharp apophysis (only *M. bonaespei* has state ββ)
- χ** Gonosquama stout, strongly chitinised and pigmented (Fig. 30)
- δ** Digitus stout, its basal third mostly covered by the large extension of the cuspis in lateral inner aspect (Fig. 31)
- ε** Aedeagus long with a prominent lateral keel and tapering tip which gets tip of gonosquama (Figs 32, 33) (group of *limata*) 30
- αα** N₁ clearly trasversal in dorsal aspect; its LA_a greater than A₁ (more often ≈ 1.35 or more) (Fig. 34)

- ββ** Metasternum with prominent sharp apophysis
χχ Gonosquama more slender, less chitinised and pigmented (Fig. 35)
δδ Digitus slender, almost completely exposed in lateral inner aspect (Fig. 36)
εε Aedeagus short, its tip far from tip of gonosquama, without lateral keel (Figs 35, 37)

35

30

- α** N_1 : high sharp lamella along its fore border with a sort of sharp spine like tooth on its anterolateral corner in dorsal aspect

31

- αα** N_1 : lamella absent either very low and incomplete. Only a weak prominence on its anterolateral corner

33

31

- α** Ratio LA/A_m of 2nd tergum in dorsal aspect about 2.9
β Ventral border of dististylus without semicircular hollow
χ Digitus with a rounded tip

limata Smith, 1855

- αα** Ratio LA/A_m of 2nd tergum in dorsal aspect about 2
ββ Ventral border of dististylus with a large semicircular hollow
χχ Digitus with a tapering tip

32

32

- α** *Secu* stripe extending on half the thickness of the flagellomeri
β N_1 with an abrupt strangling forward in dorsal aspect. Ratio LA_{max}/A_m about 2.7
χ St_3 with acute lateral lobes
δ Gonostylus with a protuberance just above the hollow

bonaespei (Turner, 1926)

- αα** *Secu* stripe extending on 4/5 the thickness of the flagellomeri
ββ N_1 evenly narrowing forward in dorsal aspect. Ratio LA_{max}/A_m about 2
χχ St_3 with blunt lateral lobes
δδ Gonostylus without any protuberance just above the hollow

sublevis (Turner, 1908)

33

- α** Anteroventral corner of N_1 with a small tooth
β N_1 : Ratio LA_{max}/A_m about 1.7. Its posterior border only slightly arched in dorsal aspect
χ Digitus not covered by cuspis, completely exposed in lateral inner aspect

cingulata (Gerstaecker, 1858)

- αα** Anteroventral corner of N_1 without any tooth
ββ N_1 : Ratio LA_{max}/A_m more than 2.5. Its posterior border strongly arched in dorsal aspect
χχ Digitus partially covered by cuspis

34

34

- α** *Secu* stripe extending only on half the thickness of the flagellomeri
β 3rd to 6th sterna with a large transversal furrow extended laterally where it forms a sort of hollow delimited by a strong rib parallel to laterotergal border
χ Dististylus with subparallel border in lateral aspect, not regularly tapering to the tip

lasiotera Boni Bartalucci, 2009

- αα** *Secu* stripe extending on more than half the thickness of the flagellomeri
ββ Sterna with only a shallow transversal furrow and without lateral ribs
χχ Dististylus regularly tapering to the tip

trachelopsila Boni Bartalucci, 2009

35

- α** Fore border of N₁ disk with a more or less upward laminated keel
- β** X₃ with a strong additional longitudinal laminated keel along its inner ventral surface (Fig. 38)
- χ** No distinct sulcus between declivitous 1st tergal and petiolar surfaces without differences between their sculpture
- δ** Well expressed basal gradulus on 7th Ter, but in *perornata* and *ornativentris* which have character state **δδ**.
- ε** Outer edge of distal gonosquama with a strong laminated keel (more often than not strongly darkened) delimiting a deep depression (hollow) on its ventral side (similar to *M. tripunctata*) and leaving exposed the inner edge in lateral aspect (Fig. 35). Only *M. ornativentris* resembles character state **εε**

36

- αα** Fore border of N₁ disk only smoothly angled either bluntly rounded without any trace of upward lamina (only *M. hermonensis* partially shows character state **α**)
- ββ** X₃ with only one laminated keel along inner surface, without any additional one
- χχ** Distinct sulcus between declivitous 1st Ter and petiolar surfaces which show different sculpture, even though without solution of the integument
- δδ** No basal gradulus on 7th Ter
- εε** Outer edge of distal gonosquama concealing most of the the inner edge in lateral aspect either evenly rounded without any keel either with a light keel (not darkened) which does not delimit a lunulated depression (hollow) on its ventral side (Fig. 39)

47

36

- α** No basal gradulus on 7th Ter

37

- αα** Well expressed basal gradulus on 7th Ter

38

37

- α** Temples deep in dorsal aspect: their depth half posterior width of the head
- β** Ventral edge of the clypeus dark and opaque
- χ** cOc broken ventrally, interrupted by hypostomal base
- δ** 2nd to 6th Ste with a deep transversal median hollow forming a sort of irregular gradulus
- ε** Outer edge of distal gonosquama with a strong laminated keel (strongly darkened) delimiting a deep depression (hollow) on its ventral side and leaving exposed the inner edge in lateral aspect
- φ** Digitus stout and sub triangular, its base as long as its height

perornata (Turner, 1908)

- αα** Temples not so deep in dorsal aspect: their depth 1/3 posterior width of the head
- ββ** Ventral edge of the clypeus light and semitransparent
- χχ** cOc complete
- δδ** Ste with even surface without transversal median hollow
- εε** Outer edge of distal gonosquama with a less strong keel not darkened and not delimiting a lunulated depression (hollow) on its ventral side, concealing the the inner edge in lateral aspect (Fig. 103)
- φφ** Digitus slender, its base half its height (Fig. 104)

ornativentris nova sp.

38

- α** Scape with two acute costulae (ribs) along its anterior border
- β** Ventral border of the clypeal lamina sub rectilinear, at most without well distinct notch

discontinua (Schultz, 1906)

- αα** Anterior border of the scape with only one rib either simply angled and rounded
- ββ** Ventral border of clypeal lamella more rounded with a more or less impressed notch

39

	39	
α	The whole either most of the fore surface of median femur smooth and pit-less	40
αα	Most of the fore surface of median femur with small p bearing very weak bristles	42
	40	
α	Fore border of pronotal disk with lamellar keel	<i>umbratica</i> (Turner 1912) & <i>impetuosa</i> (Turner, 1913)
αα	Fore border of pronotal disk with blunt keel	41
	41	
α	Rounded temples in dorsal aspect	
β	Secu stripe as large as 2/3 thickness of flagellomeri	
χ	Dense long hair on lower frons, clypeus, N ₁ disk and P almost covering underlying integument	
δ	1 st Ste completely and densely p	
ε	Dorsal edge of apical gonosquama with very short sparse hair	
φ	Volsella: long hair only on the cuspis	<i>dasymetopa</i> Boni Bartalucci, 2009
αα	Straight temples in dorsal aspect	
ββ	Secu stripe as large as entire thickness of flagellomeri	
χχ	Less dense long hair throughout not covering underlying integument	
δδ	1 st Ste almost completely pitless	
εε	Dorsal edge of apical gonosquama with long dense hair	
φφ	Volsella: very long hair on most of its surface	<i>namachorites</i> Boni Bartalucci, 2009
	42	
α	Surface of the disk of 1 st Ter bipunctate by many small p among sparse larger ones (Fig. 40)	
β	3 rd to 6 th Ste with a deep transversal furrow at ¾ of its surface persisting (extending) laterally to become parallel to laterotergal borders (Fig. 41)	43
αα	Surface of the disk of 1 st Ter with only irregular sub equal p	
ββ	3 rd to 6 th Ste with a less deep transversal furrow at ¾ of its surface and wearing out laterally	44
	43	
α	Ratio LA/A of the head in frontal aspect about 1.1	
β	Strong lamella along the fore border of pronotal disk	
χ	Em ₃ and lateral propodeal areas mostly smooth	
δ	7 th Ter Gonosquama slender. Its apical portion with subparallel edges in lateral aspect and long dense hair on its dorsal edge	
ε	White light markings	<i>leucospila</i> Boni Bartalucci, 2009
αα	Ratio LA/A of the head in frontal aspect about 1.3	
ββ	Very short lamella just on the middle of the fore border of pronotal disk	
χχ	Em ₃ and lateral propodeal areas mostly wrinkled	
δδ	Its apical portion of gonosquama tapering apically in lateral aspect without long dense hair on its dorsal edge	
εε	Yellow light markings	<i>basutorum</i> (Turner, 1913)

	44	
α	Laminated keel along fore border of pronotal disk	45
αα	Fore border of pronotal disk with only blunt keel	46
	45	
α	Secu stripe as large as thickness of flagellomeri	
β	Notch of epipygium (7 th Ter) distinctly larger than single lobe, whose length is 1 / 2.7 total length of 7 th tergum in dorsal aspect	
χ	Straight profile of 7 th tergum both in lateral and back aspect	
δ	Slender apical gonosquama in lateral aspect	
ε	Brown basic colour of metasoma	<i>servillei</i> (Guérin, 1837)
αα	Secu stripe as large as ½ thickness of flagellomeri	
ββ	Notch of epipygium (7 th Ter) as large as single lobe, whose length is 1 / 3.5 total length of 7 th tergum in dorsal aspect	
χχ	Distinctly bent profile of 7 th tergum both in lateral and back aspect	
δδ	Stout sub triangular apical gonosquama in lateral aspect	
εε	Pitch black basic colour of metasoma	<i>erythraea</i> Boni Bartalucci, 2009
	46	
α	Em ₃ and lateral propodeal areas mostly wrinkled	
β	Tarsi completely yellow	
χ	Apical belt on 3 rd to 6 th terga and sterna lemon yellow coloured, with entire fore profil	
δ	Simple mid transversal impression on 3 rd to 6 th Ste	<i>rufifrons</i> (Fabricius, 1793)
αα	Em ₃ and lateral propodeal areas mostly smooth	
ββ	Tarsi light brown	
χχ	Apical belt on 3 rd to 6 th terga and sterna creamy white coloured with laterally indented fore profile	
δδ	Strong, mid transversal impression on 3 rd to 6 th Ste to form a sort of rough gradulus	<i>fusiformis</i> (De Geer, 1778)
	47	
α	Sub triangular processes at the base of most of the bristles on the inner surface of volsella (Fig. 57)	48
αα	Inner surface of volsella simple without such processes	52
	48	
α	Trochanters, femurs and tibiae light brown	
β	Upper surface of lobes of epipygium distinctly angled in lateral aspect	
χ	Ventral surface of distal gonosquama evenly rounded without any laminated keel	
δ	Strong and crowded sub triangular processes on volsellar surface	<i>luteipes</i> Boni Bartalucci, 2005
αα	Trochanters, femurs and tibiae mostly pitch black	
ββ	Upper surface of lobes of epipygium rectilinear in lateral aspect	
αα	Ventral surface of distal gonosquama with a distinct keel along most of its length	
χχ	Weaker and more sparse sub triangular processes on volsellar surface	49

49

- α** Mesonotum (Sc_1) with a steep escarpment along its exposed anterior border and just behind the apical border of N_1
gradilis Boni Bartalucci, 2009
- αα** Mesonotum (Sc_1) normal, without such a steep escarpment along its exposed anterior border and just behind the apical border of N_1

50

50

- α** N_1 without any blunt anteroventral tooth
β Anterior surface of Es_2 mostly smooth and shining, without any **p**
χ Fore surface of the mid femurs smooth and shining with very few small **p** only at its base
vonizongo Krombein, 1949
- αα** N_1 with blunt anteroventral tooth
ββ Anterior surface of Es_2 with small **p** everywhere
χχ Fore surface of the mid femurs with small **p** all over its surface

51

51

- α** Median size: 12-14 mm
β Median suture of **PoG** well expressed by a distinct keel
χ N_1 disk: posterior **LA** less than three times median **A** in dorsal aspect (about 2.7)
δ Gonosquama slender: distal portion about twice base
ε Aedeagus stout: distal portion about 1.3 its width in lateral aspect
masaica Boni Bartalucci, 2009
- αα** Big size: 15-17 mm
ββ Median suture of **PoG** no keeled
χχ N_1 disk: posterior **LA** more than three times median **A** in dorsal aspect (about 3.2)
δδ Gonosquama stout: distal portion only 1.2 longer than base
εε Aedeagus slender: distal portion about twice its width in lateral aspect

conophora nova sp.

52

- α** Ventral surface of distal gonosquama evenly rounded (obscurely angled in *M. hermonensis*), without any laminated keel (Figs 39, 82)

53

- αα** Ventral surface of distal gonosquama with a distinct keel along most of its length (Figs 30, 35)

55

53

- α** Narrow **Secu** stripe of mid flagellomeri, about 20% thickness of the elements
mhaladai nova sp.

- αα** **Secu** stripe more than 50% thickness of mid flagellomeri

54

54

- α** **PoG** very large and flat, largest than distance oc_m/oc_1 (probably the largest one within the genus)
β Fore border of N_1 disk only smoothly angled
χ Fore surface of mid femurs completely smooth
δ Gonosquama stout with a tapering tip
ε Volsella with a stout digitus, not overcoming cuspis in lateral aspect. Short, sparse hair on its inner surface

namibensis nova sp.

$\alpha\alpha$	PoG much shorter than distance oc_m/oc₁	
$\beta\beta$	Fore border of N₁ disk angled, with a short and low acute keel just on its upper middle	
$\chi\chi$	Fore surface of mid femurs partially or entirely covered by small p bearing short weak bristles	
$\delta\delta$	Gonosquama slender	
$\epsilon\epsilon$	Volsella with a slender sub triangular digitus overcoming cuspis. Long denser hair on its inner surface	<i>hermonensis</i> nova sp.
55		
α	Ssa smooth and shining without any sort of hair	
β	Fore surface of mid femurs without any p and hairless	56
$\alpha\alpha$	Ssa roughly sculptured with scattered hair	
$\beta\beta$	Fore surface of mid femurs almost entirely covered by weak p and hair	59
56		
α	N₁ disk: horizontal fore-border waving in dorsal aspect; lateral borders with a wide notch in lateral aspect	
β	Secu stripe very large occupying half true surface of flagellomeri	<i>eterodira</i> nova spec.
$\alpha\alpha$	Entire fore border of N₁ disk sub-rectilinear both in dorsal and lateral aspect	
$\beta\beta$	Secu stripe as large as thickness of the elements at most	57
57		
α	Black, opaque ventral border of clypeal disk	
β	No ferruginous colour on metasoma	<i>aequatorialis</i> nova sp.
$\alpha\alpha$	Semitransparent ventral border of clypeal disk	
$\beta\beta$	Metasoma with extensive ferruginous colour	58
58		
α	PoG very feebly expressed. Base of Hyp large, prominent and transparent	
β	Pam shorter (8/10) than stipe	
χ	Yellow preapical stripes on the metameri as high as half the height of the element, with subrectilinear fore profile	
δ	Height of digitus 1/3 height of volsella; cuspis strongly produced, as high as digitus	<i>micruroides</i> Boni Bartalucci, 2004
$\alpha\alpha$	PoG well expressed, its area and basal Hyp flat and darkened	
$\beta\beta$	Pam 1.2 times longer than stipe	
$\chi\chi$	Yellow preapical stripes on the metameri narrow with irregular fore profile	
$\delta\delta$	Height of digitus 1/4 the height of volsella; cuspis weakly prominent, much lower than digitus	<i>pulchella</i> Boni Bartalucci, 2004
59		
α	Head sub-triangular in frontal aspect	
β	Last flagellomeri clearly thicker than basal ones	<i>rufinodis</i> (Turner, 1910)
$\alpha\alpha$	Head sub-rounded in frontal aspect	
$\beta\beta$	Even flagellomeri	60
60		
α	Basal Hyp flat and darkened	

β Ground colour of basal metameri ferruginous
rufonigra (Bingham, 1912)

αα Basal **Hyp** swollen and semitransparent
ββ No ferruginous colour on the metameri

61

61

α Clypeal disk strongly transversal, the ratio LA/A_m about 2,4
β Ratio between L_{labium}/L_{Pal} about 1.5

meruensis (Cameron, 1910)

αα Clypeal disk less transversal, the ratio LA/A_m about 2
ββ Ratio between L_{labium}/L_{Pal} about 2.3

shabeella nova sp.

Description of new species

Meria aequatorialis nova sp.

Holotypus, ♂: Congo = /Katanga 24.VIII.1958 Kuriama Kifubu J. Pasteels leg./ USNM

Male. Holotype. Figs 43-50. Body size = 14 mm.

Black. Brown mandibles, dark portions of the legs but black coxae, semitransparent tegulae, veins.

Yellow: two stripes along forward border and subapical stripe on N_1 disk; dorsal anterior tibia and basal fore-tarsomeri; basal spot on mid and hind tibiae; two small spots on 2nd **Ter**, three apical spots on 3rd to 5th **Ter**, apical narrow stripe on 6th **Ter**, two very small apical spots on 2nd to 5th **Ste**. Wings very scarcely darkened.

Irregular **p** on head and mesosoma, sparse on pronotal disk and denser on **P** disk. Irregularly bipunctate disk on 2nd to 5th **Ter**. Shallow and irregular **p** progressively sparse from 2nd to 7th **Ste**.

Completely black clypeal disk. **cOc** complete, unbroken ventrally. **PoG** well expressed, its adjacent areas flat, dark and opaque like the narrow hypostomal base. **Secu** stripe as large as thickness of flagellomeri in orthogonal aspect. Fore border of pronotal disk is harmless, simply angled, without any keel. Smooth hairless fore surface of mid femur. Ventral inner border of X_3 simply rounded, without keel. 7th **Ter** without basal gradulus. **Ste** without any transversal hollow.

Female. Unknown.

Ecology. Unknown.

Derivatio nominis. From the latitude.

Meria conophora nova sp.

Holotypus, ♂: Somalia = /British Somaliland Senag plain 29.V.1949 K.M. Guichard B.M. 1951-406/ *Meria* sp/ BMNH

Paratypi, ♂: Sudan = (1) /Sudan Gvt. Er Rowit D. King 19.5.18/ /Ent. Coll. C 8788/ BMNH. Erythraea = (1) /Africa Or./ MSNG

Male. Holotype. Figs 51-58. Body size = 17 mm.

Black. Brown dark portion of the legs. Yellow: most of clypeal disk and mandible; two large lateral stripes along anterior border and one subapical stripe on N_1 disk; spot on Es_2 ; most of $LaSt_2$; tegulae, humeral plate and basal **CC**; ventral coxae, femurs and tibiae, the whole of tarsi; broad enlarging laterally apical stripes on 1st to 6th **Ter** and 2nd to 6th **Ste**; two lateral spots on 7th **Ter** and one median on 7th **Ste**. Whitish hair throughout and hyaline wings.

p and hair more dense on clypeus and **P** where it covers underlying integument.

Semitransparent ventral border of clypeal disk. **cOc** complete, unbroken ventrally. **PoG** well expressed with a little swollen surrounding areas. **Secu** stripe large, covering about half the entire circumference of flagellomeri. Forward border of pronotal disk bluntly angled without carina and with a bulging anteroventral corner. **P** disk with a rough distinction between sub-horizontal from sub-

vertical areas. Anterior surface of mid femurs with micro **p** and hair throughout. Inner upper border of **X₃** simply rounded. 7th **Ter** without basal gradulus. **Ste** without evident transversal hollow. Gonosquama like in *M. rufinodis*. Median Inner surface of volsella with subconical processes at the base of the bristles.

Note. In habitus and size it looks like *M. cingulata*. The old record of the latter from Erythraea (BONI BARTALUCCI, 2004a) has to be removed and referred to the present taxon.

Female. Unknown.

Ecology. Unknown.

Derivatio nominis. From the Greek words κώνος (cone) and φέρω (to bring) from the presence of conical processes on the volsella.

Distribution area. African horn.

Meria hermonensis nova sp.

Holotypus, ♂: South Africa = /C.P. Hermon III.5.1968 P.J. Spangler/ USNM

Paratypi = South Africa = (1) /South Africa/ /Cape Town Jan-Apr 1915/ /J.C. Bridwell collector/ USNM; (29) /C.P. Hermon III.5.1968 P.J. Spangler/ USNM(22)-MZUF(7); (1) /South Africa C.P. 9 ml NE Wellington III-4 & 5-1968 Paul Spengler/ USNM

Male. Holotype. Figs 59-65. Body size = 14 mm.

Black. Brown: flagellum, dark portions of legs. Yellow: most of clypeal disk and mandible, tip of **Tsa**, two lateral along anterior border and one subapical on pronotal disk, tegulae, apical coxae and femurs, most of tibiae, tarsi, apical stripe with waving fore edge on 1st **Ter**, apoical stripes strongly indented laterally on 2nd to 6th **Ter** and **Ste**. Wings hyaline, hair whitish. **p** like *M. tripunctata*.

PoG well detectable, its areas flat and opaque. **cOc** complete ventrally. **Secu** stripe about 90% thickness of the elements in orthogonal aspect. Anterior border of pronotal disk is bluntly angled but very short keeled tracts laterally to the median notch. Forward surface of mid femur covered by shallow small **p** bearing very weak hair. **X₃** with rounded inner ventral edge. 7th **Ter** without basal gradulus. **Ste** without noticeable transversal hollow. Gonosquama with rounded ventral surface with very long hair on apical tip.

Coloration and size (13-15 mm) poorly variable.

Female. Unknown.

Derivatio nominis. From the typical locality.

Note. Distinct species by the unarmed gonosquama together with flat postgenal areas, punctured forward surface of mid femurs, lack of additional laminated keel on **X₃** and basal gradulus on 7th **Ter**.

Meria heterodira nova sp.

Holotypus, ♂: Botswana = /Botswana (B3) 18 mls NE Kalkfontein 12-13.IV.1972/ /Southern African Exp. B.M. 1972-I/ BMNH

Male. Holotype. Figs 66-74. Body size = 8.5 mm.

Black, brown, pale yellow and bright ferruginous. Flagellum, hypostomal areas, veins and dark portions of the legs are brown. Pale yellow: most of mandibles; sub-apical stripe on pronotal disk; fore half tegulae; humeral plate; very small spot on apical femurs, basal tibiae, tarsi; very narrow median apical spot on 1st **Ter**, three small apical spots (the median larger than laterals) on 2nd to 6th **Ter**, two small lateral on 2nd to 6th **Ste**. Ferruginous: almost the entire 1st (but upper and base of petiole), 2nd and 7th metameri, postgradular 3rd **Ter**, lateral 4th **Ter**, part of 3rd **Ste**. Sparse **p** on vertex, upper frons, most of pronotal disk. **P** with detectable space among **p**. 1st and 7th **Ter** almost smooth, 2nd to 6th **Ste** with punctured anterior and smooth posterior surfaces. Whitish hair and hyaline wings.

Dark brown ventral lamella of clypeal disk. Broad **Secu** stripe as large as half the entire circumference of flagellomeri. **cOc** complete, unbroken ventrally. **PoG** narrow, its area very swollen and semitransparent. Pronotal disk: anterior border angled and waved, without any carina; laterally with vertical rows of **p**. **Em₃** and lateral propodeal areas wrinkled. Anterior surface of median femur smooth and hairless. **X₃** with a rounded inner upper border. 1st tergal surface with rare small **p** among

irregularly settled larger ones. No gradulus on 7th **Ter**. Even surfaces of **Ste**. Gonosquama like in *M. rufinodis*.

Note. Very similar in habitus to small specimens of *M. rufinodis* from which is well known by shape of the head in frontal aspect, pronotum, epipygium and genitalia, the swollen **Pog** areas.

Female. Unknown.

Ecology. Unknown.

Derivatio nominis. From the Greek words 'έτερος = different and δειρή = neck, because of the odd shape of the pronotum.

Meria namibensis nova sp.

Holotypus, ♂: Angola = /Angola Huila District J. Balfour-Browne B.M. 1954-797/ /Peviva ca 30 ml E of Porto Alexandre 24-27.VI.1954 Flying around yellow succulent on flowers (n° 90)/ /Stn N° 293/ BMNH

Paratypi ♂: Angola = (5) /Angola Huila District J. Balfour-Browne B.M. 1954-797/ /Peviva ca 30 ml E of Porto Alexandre 24-27.VI.1954 Flying around yellow succulent on flowers (n° 90)/ /Stn N° 293/ BMNH(4)-MZUF(1)

Male. Holotype. Figs 75-84. Body size = 13 mm.

Black, pale yellow. Pale yellow: large transversal spo on clypeal disk; basal mandible; small spot on **Tsa**; two stripes along anterior border and subapical one on pronotal disk; fore half tegula; apical femurs; the whole of tibiae and tarsi; narrow stripe having a laterally indented fore edge on 1st to 6th **Ter**; two lateral and one median spots on 2nd **Ste**. Hair whitish and wings hyaline. Punctuation without distinct features.

Dark and opaque ventral mid border of the clypeal disk. **cOc** complete. **PoG** well expressed, one fourth of **FoO** (from the base to clypeus), with ill defined median suture. **Secu** stripe as large as thickness of the elements. Simpe bluntly angled anterior border of pronotal disk. **Em**₃ mostly smooth and shining. Most of the anterior surface of mid femurs smooth devoid of micro hair. **X**₃ with only one lamellar keel along its inner surface. Basal 7th **Ter** with no gradulus. Gonosquama simple with rounded apical ventral surface.

Note. Well distinct taxon by the large **PoG**, probably the most produced in the males of the genus, and genitalia.

Female. Unknown.

Ecology. Unique information from the label.

Variability. Poor both in colour and size.

Derivatio nominis. From Namibe, the name of the southern Region of Angola.

Meria noorti nova sp.

Holotypus, ♀: South Africa = /Jeffrey's bay - S.A.M. 1:60/ /SAM HYM A0/

Female. Holotype Figs 85-86. Body size 9.5 mm.

Black body. Brown: antennae, mandibles, clypeal lamella, semitransparent base of **Hyp**, veins and legs. Creamy white: small lateral spots on 2nd to 3rd terga. Dark ferruginous: apical shadows on 1st and 2nd terga, 3rd tergum (but sides), apical 2nd sternum, 3rd sternum, 4th to 6th metameri. Wings slightly darkened. Brownish hai on clypeus, lighter to whitish elsewhere. Well distinct median furrow on the lower frons. Clypeus almost entirely covered by densely packed **p**. **cOc** broadly interrupted by the swollen base of **Hyp**. Mandible without lobe along its inner edge. **N**₁ disk with a belt of **p** along its anterior border, with sparse **p** elsewhere; lateral **N**₁ almost entirely **p**. **Es**₂ entirely covered by dense regular **p**, but its extreme posterior corner. **Em**₃ smooth. Fore wing with 2nd **CSM**. **P** disk largely **p** with only obscure wrinkles laterally, with short median furrow. Lateral **P** smooth and pitless and so posterior **P** too, but lower median area. No basal gradulus on 3rd tergum.

Note. Very near to *M. dissimilis* from which is well known in habitus, different clypeal **p**, strong furrow on lower frons.

Meria ordinaria nova sp.

Holotypus, ♀: Tanzania = /Tanzania Mkomazi Game Res., Ibaya 3°58'S 37°48'E 24 Jan 1996 A. Russel- Smith ex pitfall traps Burnt grassland/ /SAM HYM A019844/

Paratypi, ♀: Tanzania = (1) /Tanzania Mkomazi Game Res., Ibaya 3°58'S 37°48'E 6 Sept. 1995 A. Russel- Smith ex pitfall traps Burnt grassland/ /SAM HYM A019769/ (1) /Tanzania Mkomazi Game Res., Ibaya 3°58'S 37°48'E 12 Oct 1995 A. Russel- Smith ex pitfall traps Burnt grassland/ /SAM HYM A019739/

Female. Holotype Figs 88-95. Body size 7.5 mm.

Dark brown to ferruginous brown. Lighter brown: ventral head, most of pronotal disk, Upper **coxae** and femurs, 1st and shadows on 2nd **Ter**. Ferruginous brown: antennae, clypeal disk, hypostoma, **LaSt**₂, semitransparent tegulae, veins, ventral **coxae**, tibiae, tarsi, most of metasoma.

At the base of 2nd **Ter** there are two lateral ill defined lighter small spots. Yellowish hair throughout.

cOc complete. **PoG** short but well expressed, surrounding areas gently swollen. **P** disk densely wrinkled laterally and posteriorly. Pterostigma larger than 1st **CSM**. 2nd **CSM** lacking. Gradulus present at the base of 2nd and 3rd **Ter**.

Male unknown. Specimens of *M. meruensis* (♂) and *M. peripatetica* (♀) are seized in the same period and place,; in the same areas *M. rufitarsis* (♀) and *M. impetuosa* (♂) exist, so it is impossible to make right sex associations without certain field observations and data.

Ecology. Unknown.

Derivation nominis. Because of its plain habitus.

Variability. Size of the paratypi are 5 and 6.5 mm.

Note. Distinguished taxon by the shape of ventral lamella of the clypeus, large basal element of **Pam**, large pterostigma, wrinkled **P**.

Meria ornativentris nova sp.

Holotypus, ♂: Namibia = /SW Aus. Africa Jan. 1930/ /R.E. Turner Brit. Mus. 1930-117/ BMNH

Male. Holotype. Figs 96-105. Body size = 16 mm.

Dark brown. Creamy yellow: most of clypeal disk; tip of the scape; mandibles; two lateral along anterior border and one subapical stripes an pronotal disk; fore half tegulae; apical femurs, tibiae and tarsi entirely, apex of ventral **X**₃; apical stripe with waving fore edge on 1st, strongly indented laterally from 2nd to 6th **Ter**; median irregular spot on 7th **Ter**; two lateral and two median small apical spots on 2nd to 6th **Ste**.

Bright ferruginous: the whole of metasoma, with brown shadings on petiole, mid of 1st to 6th **Ter**.

Wings hyaline. Dense white hair, partly covering underlying integumente on lower frons, clypeal disk, **Tsa**, lateral **N**₁, **Es**₁, lateral **Es**₂, lateral **Sc**₂, postscutellar area **N**₃, most of **P** but anteroventral corner.

Semitransparent ventral lamella of clypeal disk. **cOc** shortly broken ventrally. **Hyp** area swollen with undetectable **PoG**. **Secu** stripe about 2/3 thickness of the flagellomeri. Bluntly angled anterior border of **N**₁ disk. Lateral **N**₁ with a median stripe of sub horizontal wrinkles followed by a smooth area adjacent to posteriore border. **P** disk with area horizontalis well detectable from area verticalis. Anterior surface of mid femur smooth and shining. **X**₃ with two longitudinal laminated keels. No basal gradulus on 7th **Ter**. Surfaces of **Ste** with a very shallow transversal impression. Gonosquama like in Fig. 103, approaching the pattern of *M. rufinodis*.

Female. Unknown.

Ecology. Unknown.

Derivatio nominis. From the variegated metasoma.

Note. Distinguished taxon by the shape of epipygium in dorsal aspect, colour of metasoma and mainly by the shape of gonosquama.

Meria peripatetica nova sp.

Holotypus, ♀: Tanzania = /Tanzania Mkomazi Game Res., Ibaya 3°58'S 37°48'E 21 Dec. 1995 A. Russel- Smith ex pitfall traps Burnt grassland/ /SAM HYM A019800/

Paratypus, ♀: Tanzania = (1) /Tanzania Mkomazi Game Res., Ibaya 3°58'S 37°48'E 15 Nov. 1995 A. Russel-Smith ex pitfall traps Burnt grassland/ /SAM HYM A019704/

Female. Holotype Figs 106-113. Body size 7.0 mm.

Brown to light brown, whitish.

Antennae, most mandible, semitransparent tegulae, **LaSt₂**, legs, large shadows on metasoma. Two lateral apical whitish spots on 2nd and 3rd **Ter**. Fore wing darkened, hind wing hyaline. White hair throughout, longer on outer **Es₂** and lateral **P**.

PoG well developed, while **Sc₁** is very narrow, as it happens normally in strongly brachypterous forms, with reduced parapsidal lines and notauli.

Male. Unknown. See under *M. ordinaria*.

Ecology. Unknown.

Derivatio nominis. From the greek term περιπατητικός = walking, because of its inability to flight.

Note. Strongly different from *M. neavei* the only other unfit to flight form known from Afrotropical Region.

Meria shabeella nova sp.

Holotypus, ♂: Somalia = /Somalia Afgoi Lower Shabelli valley 6-20.III.1977 Mal. Trap F. Bin/ RMNH

Male. Holotype. Figs 114-121. Body size = 14.5 mm.

Black. Brown: dark portions of the leg, mandibles, flagellum, veins, lighter pterostigma, apical metasoma. Yellow: the whole of the clypeal disk but the semitransparent ventral border; most of mandible; apex of **Tsa**; two large stripe along forward border and one subapical stripe on **N₁** disk; spot on **Es₂**; apical femurs, most of tibiae, the whole of tarsi; large apical belt on 1st to 6th **Ter**, narrower on 2nd to 6th **Ste** and two spots on 7th **Ter**. Hyaline wings and whitish hair throughout.

cOc complete. Base of **Hyp** and **PoG** areas swollen. **Secu** stripe larger than thickness of flagellomeri. Simply angled, without any keel, fore border of **N₁** disk. Anterior surface of mid femurs with small **p** and hair throughout. **X₃** with only one laminated keel. 7th **Ter** without basal gradulus. Gonosquama like in *M. rufinodis*.

Female. Unknown.

Ecology. Unknown.

Derivatio nominis. From the name of the Shabeelle river.

Note. Similar in habitus to *M. aequatorialis* from which is well known by the shape of the head in dorsal aspect, different **Pam**, **N₁** in dorsal aspect, 7th **Ter** in dorsal aspect, volsella.

Meria mhaladai nova sp.

Holotypus, ♂: Zimbabwe = /Zimbabwe 50 km S Bulawayo Matubo 3-5.12.98 leg. Marek Halada/ OLML

Paratypi: South Africa = (2) /South Africa Mooketsi Transvaal Feb 17 1968 Krombein & Spangler/ USNM(1)-MZUF(1); (1) /South Africa Mooketsi Feb 17 1968 Krombein & Spangler/ USNM; (1) /South Africa Trsvl. Mooketsi 14-18 Feb 1968 Krombein & Spangler/ USNM; Zimbabwe = (1) /W Zimbabwe 60 km N Bulawayo Mariposa Rd. XII 1995 leg M. Snižek/ OLML

Male. Holotype. Figs 122-130. Body size = 12 mm.

Black, brown, yellow. Brown: apical mandible, antennae with rufous colour on ventral flagellomeri) veins, dark portions of the legs (but fore **X**), **LaSt₂**. Yellow: spot on median clypeal disk, two narrow subapical stripes on pronotal disk, small spot on outer **Es₂**, inner side of tegulae, apical femurs, most of tibiae, entire tarsi, very narrow apical stripe on 1st **Ter**, three apical spots on 2nd to 5th **Ter**, waving stripe on 6th **Ter**, two very small spots on 2nd to 6th **Ste**.

Whitish hair and hyaline wings. Opaque ventral border of clypeal disk. **cOc** complete. **PoG** area swollen and opaque. **Secu** stripe very narrow, only about 25% thickness of flagellomeri. Anterior border of pronotal disk bluntly angled without any carina. **su₃** simple, without any pattern like a stitch. Anterior surface of median femur with small **p** and hair. Upper inner edge of **X₃** simply rounded. 7th **Ter** without basal gradulus. **Ste** with even surface. Gonosquama without any keel on its distal ventral border.

Female. Unknown.

Derivatio nominis. From the name of collector.

Note. Taxon well featured by narrow **Secu** stripe and simple gonosquama.

Poecilotiphia Cameron, 1902

Poecilotiphia CAMERON (1902: 274)

Poecilotiphia: GORBATOVSKY (1981: 383-386)

Poecilotiphia: BONI BARTALUCCI (2001: 28-32)

Only with some uncertainty I decided to include the following new taxa in the genus *Poecilotiphia*. In fact no record neither description of any male with the features of the genus from Austral Africa exist. Nevertheless the specimens here described share characters only with Palaearctic females of the Cameron's genus: the reduction of palpomeri (shared only with *Zezelda*) and mainly the lack of the solution of the integument between 1st tergal and petiolar surfaces, a character state which segregates it from all the other females of the subtribe: *Meria* (ILLIGER, 1807; BONI BARTALUCCI, 2004b), *Meriodes* (BONI BARTALUCCI, 2007), *Macromeria* (SAUNDERS, 1850), *Afromeria* (BONI BARTALUCCI, 2007) and *Zezelda* (ARGAMAN, 1994).

Poecilotiphia australis nova sp.

Holotypus, ♀: Namibia = /Upper Ostrich gorge 22°29'S 14°69'E Swakopmund Dist. 20 Nov.-18 Dec 1984 J. Irish, H. Liessner/ NNIC/NMNW

Female. Holotype Figs 131-141. Body size = 7.5 mm.

Brown. Clypeal disk, mandible, antennae, hypostomal area, legs but coxae, are light brown. Metasoma is ferruginous brown. Wings hyaline. Veins colourless. Pterostigma transparent light yellow. Most of the body punctureless and shining. Lateral **P** with weak sub vertical wrinkles. **P** disk with sparse **p** and fine transversal wrinkles all over its surface, more impressed on the declivitous surface. No basal gradulus on 2nd and 3rd **Ter. sul** only on 1st **Ter.**

Typical features of *Poecilotiphia*: sub rectilinear profile of the frons and pronotum in lateral aspect; very transversal clypeal disk; Reduced **FoO** and long **PoG**; dense **p** with long bristles all over its length on the upper scape; mandible without inner upper lobe in frontal spect; reduced palpomeri, with **Pam** 4- and **Pal** 3- segmented; large pterostigma without inner distinct areola; forecoxa without inner ventral longitudinal carinated keel; shape of foretibial spur; lacking of short tuft of hair on apical tibia and basal tarsomerus of fore leg; ultimate hind-tarsomerus shorter than penultimate; no sulcus between upper petiolar and declivitous 1st tergal surfaces; metameri with lateral semicircular row of points.

It resembles to *Poecilotiphia lacteipennis* in general habitus.

Male. Unknown.

Ecology. Unknown.

Derivatio nominis. From the austral region.

Poecilotiphia idioptera nova sp.

Holotypus, ♀: Namibia = /Gochenagas 218 Windhoek 22°49'S 17°12'E 22 Dec 1981- 20 Jan 1982 Preser. Trap M.L. Penrith/ NMNW/NMNW

Female. Holotype Figs 142-151. Body size = 9.5 mm.

Dark brown to brown head and mesosoma. Ferruginous: metasoma with darker shadows on 1st **Ter.** Yellowish hair throughout. Sparse **p** on mesosoma. **P** disk largely smooth with **p** only on its antero-lateral corner and perimetral edge. Lateral **P** smooth without any trace of wrinkles. Wings hyaline. Stout and thick head in dorsal aspect. Scape closer to *Meria* pattern. Short tuft of hair on inner edge of basal 1st and 2nd fore tarsomeri. Fore wing with a quadrangular 2nd **CSM**. Fore coxa with a keel on its ventral inner edge and row of **p** on **Ter** like in *Meria*. It shows the following characters of *Poecilotiphia*: large **PoG**, reduced **FoO**, mandible without inner upper lobe, reduced palpal formula:

Pam 5- Pal 3- segmented, shape of fore tibial spur, ultimate hindtarsomerus shorter than penultimate, lack of the transversal sulcus with solution of the integument between 1st tergal and petiolar surfaces. Male. Unknown.

Ecology. Unknown.

Derivatio nominis. From the Greek words ἴδιος = particular and πτηρόν = wing, because of the particular venation of the forewing.

Note. Taxon with some character states closer to *Meria*, but it possess the main autapomorphies within the tribe characterizing *Poecilotiphia*.

***Zezelda* Argaman, 1994**

Zezelda ARGAMAN (1994: 90)

Zezelda stigma (Turner, 1912) ♂

Myzine stigma: TURNER (1912: 699-700)

Zezelda stigma BONI BARTALUCCI (2007: 1289)

Myzine pernicioso: TURNER (1913: 728) [Holotypus, ♀: South Africa = /Algoa bay Capland 22.1.96 Dr Brauns/ /*Myzine* (*Pseudomeria*) *pernicioso* Turn Type/ /Type Turner/ (red) /*Pseudomeria pernicioso* type ♀ Turner/ (yellow) /Type Hym 0341 *Pseudomeria pernicioso* Turner/ (red) TM !. **Nova syn.**

M. pernicioso looks like *Poecilotiphia* females in general aspect and wings, shows similar reduction of the mouthparts with **Pal 4-** and **Pam 5-**segmented and the same fore tibial spur, but it presents a distinct median sulcus with solution of the integument between 1st tergal and petiolar surface. Also *M. stigma* shows a similar complex of character states different from other taxa. Also because of proximity of their typical localities to propose their synonymy seems to be a justifiable hazard.

***Meriodes* Boni Bartalucci, 2007**

Meriodes BONI BARTALUCCI (2007: 1278)

Males of the group are mainly featured from *Meria* by distinct placoids on the antenna and the clear solution of the integument between 1st tergal and upper petiolar surface; the last character state is only present in the males of *Allomeria* and *Notomeria* within the tribe.

***Meriodes laticeps* nova sp.**

Holotypus, ♂ - South Africa = /Hester Malan N.R. 10 mls E Springbok 7-8.1.1972/ /Southern African Expe. B.M. 1972-I/ BMNH

Paratypi, ♂ - South Africa = (2) /South Africa Western Cape Travellers Rest. Sevilla 32°04.394S 19°04.833E 328 m 12.i.2008 R. stanway R854 pollinating Buchu sp. Dry Mountain Fynbos/ SAM(1)-MZUF(1); (1) /RSA Cape 40 km S Lamberts bay 30.X.999 Leg. Marek Halada/ OLML

Male. Holotype. Figs. 152-162. Body size = 10.5 mm.

Black. Brown: **PoG** areas, antenna, tip of mandible, veins, dark portions of the legs. Ivory white: basal mandible, subapical stripe on pronotal disk, apical fore and mid femurs, dorsal tibiae, all the tarsi but apical hind tarsomerus, three apical small spots on 2nd to 6th **Ter**, two very small apical spots on 2nd to 5th **Ste**. Wings hyaline. Hair whitish. Regularly **p** throughout, sparser on vertex and lower genae, but smooth 1st tergal surface and pregradular areas on 3rd to 6th **Ste**.

PoG areas slightly swollen. 4th to final flagellomeres with placoids. No keel along fore border of pronotal disk which is simply angled. **P** with roughly detectable subhorizontal from sub vertical areas. Semi globular 1st **Ter**. Strong gradulus slightly invaginated like a shallow colpus on 2nd to 6th **Ter** and 4th to 6th **Ste**.

Ecology. Only note on the label of paratypes from Dry Mountain.

Female. Unknown.

Derivatio nominis. Latin name indicating large head.

Note. Distinct from other species of the genus by the large head in frontal aspect, placoids, shape of genitalia and last by the major size.

New synonyms and combinations with designation of Lectotypes

Meria discontinua (Schultz, 1906)

Plesia interrupta: CAMERON (1905: 318 ♂)

Plesia discontinua: SCHULTZ (1906: 162 ♂)

Myzine inconspicua: TURNER (1913: 731-732 ♀) **Nova syn.**

Plesia interrupta: JACOT GUILLARMOD (1961: 4 ♂)

Meria inconspicua: BONI BARTALUCCI (2009: 1840)

♀

South Africa = (8) /South Africa/ /Cape Town Jan-Apr 1915/ /J.C. Bridwell Collector/ USNM; (3) /R.S.A. Western Cape 60 km N Cape Town 9.XI.1999 leg. M. Halada/ OLML; (1) /S. Africa R.E. Turner Brit. Mus. 1929-96/ /Cape Province Worcester January 1929/ /*Meria inconspicua* (Turn.) det 1950 C. Jacot-Guillarmod/ BMNH; (1) /South Africa W. Cape Cape of Good Hope Nat. Res. Olifantsbos 34°16'S 18°23'E 28-30 March 1995 S. Van Noort Yellow pan trap Strand Veld/ /SAM-HYM A020758/

♂

Namibia = (1) /SW Africa Okahandja 2-4.ii.1972/ /Southern Africa Exped. 1972-I/ BMNH

South Africa = (23) /South Africa/ /Cape Town Jan-Apr 1915/ /J.C. Bridwell Collector/ USNM; (4) /R.S.A. W. Cape Lamberts Bay coast 29.X.1999 leg. M. Halada/ OLML; (4) /R.S.A. W. Cape 40 km S Lamberts Bay 30.X.1999 leg. M. Halada/ OLML; (1) /R.S.A. W. Cape Greyton 7.XI.1999 Rivieronderend r leg. Marek Halada/ OLML; (15) /R.S.A. Western Cape 60 km N Cape Town 9.XI.1999 leg. M. Halada/ OLML; (1) /Soth Africa Cape P. Brandfontein reserve 34°46'S 19°52'E 14-18-October 1992 S. Van Noort/ /SAM-HYM A020757/

Note. The synonymy is here proposed on the ground of the identity of labels and the intuition by Turner, who nevertheless did not establish it. JACOT-GUILLARMOD (1961) confirmed the substitution of Cameron's name performed by SCHULTZ (1906).

Meria meruensis (Cameron, 1910)

Plesia meruensis: CAMERON (1910: 239-240) [Lectotype ♂, here designated to ensure name's proper and consistent use: **Kenya** = /Meru Nieder/ /Sjostedt/ /Okt/ /*Plesia meruensis Cam Type*/ /NHRS HEVA 00000925/. Paralectotype: /Meru Nieder/ /Sjostedt/ /Ngane nr Nyuki/ /♂/ /NHRS HEVA00000926!/]

Note. It could be the male of *M. rufitarsis* because of identity of labels, but males have been caught with females of *M. peripatetica* too, so more informations are needed about to decide the exact coupling.

Meria rufitarsis (Cameron, 1910)

Myzine (Meira) rufitarsis: CAMERON (1910: 240-241) [Lectotype ♀, here designated to ensure name's proper and consistent use: **Kenya** = /Meru Nieber/ /Sjostedt/ /29 Dec/ /*Meria rufitarsis Cam Type*/ /NHRS HEVA 00000927!/]

Meria sublevis (Turner, 1908)

Myzine sublevis: TURNER (1908:500-501) [Lectotype ♀, here designated to ensure name's proper and consistent use: **South Africa** = /Del B - 83 27/ /LT♀/ (rounded) /*Myzine (Hemimeria) sublevis Turn Type*/ /Type/ (rounded with red outer ring) /B.M. Type Hym 15.1518/ BMNH!]

Meria neavei (Turner, 1911)

Myzine (Pseudomeria) neavei: TURNER (1911: 614-615) [Lectotype ♀, here designated to ensure name's proper and consistent use: **South Africa** = /Nyasaland Mombera distr. 4000 ft. 15-19 June 1910 S.A. Neave/ /1910 353/ /*Myzine (Pseudomeria) neavei Turn Type*/ /Type/ (rounded with red outer ring) /B.M-Type Hym. 15.1514/ BMNH!]

***Meria umbratica* (Turner, 1912)**

Myzine umbratica: TURNER (1912: 702) [Lectotype ♀, here designated to ensure name's proper and consistent use: South Africa = /???????? S ???? Capland 15.1.06 Dr. Brauns/ /Brauns Coll. 1912-44/ 22/ /*Myzine umbratica* Turn. Type/ /Type/ (rounded with red outer ring) /B.M. Type Hym. 15.1517/ BMNH!]

***Meria basatorum* (Turner, 1913)**

Myzine basatorum: TURNER (1913: 736) [Lectotype ♂, here designated to ensure name's proper and consistent use: South Africa = /Basutoland R Crawshay 1902-64/ /*Myzine basatorum* Turn, Type/ /Type/ (rounded with red outer ring) /B.M. Type Hym. 15121/ BMNH!]

***Meria impetuosa* (Turner, 1913)**

Myzine impetuosa: TURNER (1913: 736-737) [Lectotype ♂, here designated to ensure name's proper and consistent use: Kenya = /Brit. E. Africa Foot of Kikuyu escarpmentr. Naivajha 7300 ft March 3, 1911 S.A. Neave/ /1911-177/ /*Myzine impetuosa* Turn Type/ /Type/ (rounded with red outer ring) /B.M. Type Hym 15.1520/ BMNH!]

Note. See under *M.umbratica*.

***Afromeria anomala* (Boni Bartalucci, 2007)**

Meria anomala: BONI BARTALUCCI (2007: 1837, ♂ Figs 92-102) (as *Meria leucospila* because of "lapsus calami").

Note. Presence of large sensilla basiconica on flagellomeres, shape of the collar in dorsal aspect, conical processes on **St**₃, the lack of thickened hair on dorsal hind tarsomeres, the strongly transversal 1st metamerus and short petiole, the presence of flattened bristles at the sides of apical terga (even if very few and short), suggest to take away this taxon from the genus *Meria* and insert it into the genus *Afromeria*, with some degree of doubt.

New records

***Meria fusiformis* (De Geer, 1778)**

Apis fusiformis: DE GEER (1778: 608)

Meria fusiformis: BONI BARTALUCCI (2004a: 380-384)

♀

Namibia = (1) /S.W. Africa Hofflung 9-16.x.1933 K. Jordan/ /Brit. Muas. 1934-110/ BMNH

South Africa = (12) /R.S.A. W Cape 40 km S Lamberts Bay 30.X.1999 leg. Marek Halada/ OLML; (2) /Cape Prov Saf Pt Elizabeth/ /I 1957 NHL Krauss/ USNM; (1) /South Africa Western Cape Travellers rest. Sevilla 32°04.374'S 19°04.837'E 328 m Dry Mountain Fynbos no data given/ /SAM-HYM A021955/; (1) /*Bloemfont' n Oraniye F.? 29.IX.1914/* CUIC; (1) /Mossel Bay So. Africa Mar-Apr 1930 R.E. Turner/ /Cornell U lot 805/ CUIC

♂

South Africa = (2) /*Vil en hage C.P. 15.XI.60 J.S. Taylor/* USNM; (11) /R.S.A. W Cape 40 km S Lamberts Bay 30.X.1999 leg. Marek Halada/ OLML; (4) /Mossel Bay So. Africa Mar-Apr 1930 R.E. Turner/ /Cornell U lot 805/ CUIC

***Meria rufifrons* (Fabricius, 1793)**

Larra rufifrons: FABRICIUS (1793: 222)

Meria spinolae: WESTWOOD (1835: 53)

Meria rufifrons: JACOT GUILLARMOD (1961: 3-4, under *Myzine (Meira) violaceipennis* Cameron, 1905 as its synonym)

♀

Zimbabwe = (1) /Rhodesia Salisbury A.Watsham- Nov 68/ BMNH; (1) /South Africa Trsvl Mooketsi 14-18-Feb. 1968 Krombein & Spangler/ USNM

♂

South Africa = (2) /South Africa Trsvl. 5ml W Warmbad 24-25 Feb. 1968 Krombein & Spangler/ USNM(1)-MZUF(1)

***Meria limata* (Smith, 1855)**

Meria limata: SMITH (1855: 81)

Meria limata: BONI BARTALUCCI (2009: 1842)

♂

Namibia = (2) /S.W. Africa (W48) Kombat 1-6.iv.1972/ /Southern African Exp. B.M. 1972-1/ BMNH

South Africa = (1) /S. Africa. Cape province 14 km e. Jeffrey's bay, roadside 17 Feb '74 A.B. Gurney/ USNM; (1) /South Africa Trsvl 5 ml W Warmbad II- 24-25- 1968 Paul J. Spangler/ USNM

***Meria cingulata* (Gerstaecker, 1858)**

Myzine cingulata: GERSTAECKER (1858: 512)

Meria cingulata: BONI BARTALUCCI (2004a: 385-386)

♂

Zimbabwe = (2) /S. Rhodesia Matopo Hills iv.1932/ /Miss. A. Mackie/ BMNH

***Meria meruensis* (Cameron, 1910)**

♂

Tanzania = (1) /Tanzania. Mkomazi Game Reserve, Ibaya camp 3°58'S 37°48'E 29Jan-11mar 1996/ /S. van Noort malaise trap *Acacia/Commiphora/Combretum* bushland/ /SAM HYM A018199/; (1) /Tanzania. Mkomazi Game Reserve, Ibaya hill 3°58'S 37°47'E 15-30 April 1996/ /S. van Noort malaise trap *Acacia/Commiphora/Combretum* bushland/ /SAM HYM A018199/

***Meria perornata* (Turner, 1908)**

Myzine (Pseudomeria) perornata: TURNER (1908: 499-500)

Meria perornata: BONI BARTALUCCI (2009: 1842)

♂

South Africa = (1) /Feb 1915 Moryo Basutoland Afr. Cornell lot 447 sub H. Junod/ CUIIC

***Meria sublevis* (Turner, 1908)**

Myzine sublevis: TURNER (1908: 500-501)

Meria sublevis: BONI BARTALUCCI (2009: 1839-1840)

♀ (Fig. 21)

Namibia = (1) /S.W. Africa (31) Okahandja 2-4.II.1972/ /Southern African Exp. B.M. 1972-1/ BMNH

South Africa = (2) /Masiene P. Elizabeth Afr. R.F. Lawrence/ /SAM-HYM A022575/

Zambia = (1) /Zambia Mochi/ MSNP

♂

Angola = (3) /Angola (A37) 5mls NE Negola 25.iii.1972/ /Southern African Exp. B.M. 1972-1/ BMNH

Botswana = (1) /Botswana (B1) 42 mls W Kalkfontein 11-12.iv.192/ /Southern African Exp. B.M.1972-1/ BMNH;

(1) /Botswana (B7) Kuke Pan 20°59'S 22°25'E 14-15.iv.192/ /Southern African Exp. B.M. 1972-1/ BMNH; (1)

/Botswana (B8) L. Ngami 2 mls NE Sehitwa 15-16.iv.192/ /Southern African Exp. B.M. 1972-1/ BMNH; (1)

/Botswana (B11) Moremi Reserve 19°23'S 23°33'E 18-20.iv.192/ /Southern African Exp. B.M. 1972-1/ BMNH;

Mozambique = (1) /Mozambique Lourenco Marquez/ /ii 1957 NLHKrauss/ USNM; (2) /Lourenco Marquez Cornell

lot 447 Sub 137 H. Junod/ CUIIC; (1) Lour. Marquez Port E. Africa Herman Junod/ CUIIC; (14) /Lour. Marquez

Port E. Africa Herman Junod/ /Cornell U. lot 447 sub 63/ CUIIC(11)-MZUF(3); (1) /Rikatla Lourenco Marquez

Nov-Dec 14 Sub H. Junod/ /Lourenco Marquez H. Junod Africa/ CUIIC; (2) /Rikatla Lourenco Marquez *Apr 1915*

Sub H. Junod/ /Lourenco Marquez H. Junod Africa/ CUIIC; (1) /Lour. Marquez Port E. Africa *May 1915* Herman

Junod/ CUIIC; (1) /Lourenco Marq. Africa *Feb 1917* H. Junod/ CUIIC

Namibia = (1) /S.W. Africa (3) Noachabeb 27mls NNE Grunau 10-12.I.1972/ /Southern African Exp. B.M. 1972-

1/ BMNH; (1) /S.W. Africa Regenstein nr. Windhoek 22°42'S 17°02'E/ /6500-7600 ft 8.ii.1972 BMNH(E) 1972-1/

BMNH; (4) /S.W. Africa (31) Okahandja 2-4.II.1972/ /Southern African Exp. B.M. 1972-1/ BMNH; (2) /S.W.

Africa (W52) Swakop R. 3mls S Okahandja 7.iv.1972/ /Southern African Exp. B.M. 1972-1/ BMNH

South Africa = (3) /Feb 1915 Moryo Basutoland Afr. Cornell lot 447 sub H. Junod/ CUIIC

Zambia = (1) /Zambia Sesheke summer 1989, mal. trap. W. Slobbe, RMNH/; (1) /Zambia (nr Namibian border)

Sesheke c. 950 m iv-xii.1990 mal. trap. W. Slobbe RMNH/

Zimbabwe = (2) /N. Rhodesia 85 miles W of Kariba Gorge 24.6.10 Silverlock coll. 1912-20/ BMNH

Meria rufinodis (Turner, 1910)

Myzine rufinodis: TURNER (1910: 392-393)

Meria rufinodis: BONI BARTALUCCI (2004a: 391-394-395)

♂

Namibia = (1) /S.W. Africa (36) Otjikoko Sud Fm. 33 mls ENE Omaruru 10-13.ii.1972/ /Southern African Exp. B.M. 1972-1/ BMNH; (1) /Namibia Bogenfels 21 = ct. 1977 VB Whitehead/ /SAM-HYM A020766/

South Africa = (2) /Capland Willowmore Dec. 1912 Dr. Brauns/ /South African Museum ex National Museum Bulawayo 1981/ /SAM-HYM A003151/

Meria rufonigra (Bingham, 1912)

Myzine rufonigra: BINGHAM (1912: 559-560)

Meria rufonigra: BONI BARTALUCCI (2004a: 394, 396-397)

♂

Zambia = (1) /Zambia Sesheke 1989 W. Slobbe RMNH02/

Zimbabwe = (13) /Rhodesia Matopos Nat'l. Pk. IV 1&2 Feb-1968 Paul J. Spangler/ USNM(10)-MZUF(2)-OLML(1)

Meria umbratica (Turner, 1912)

♀ (Fig. 22)

South Africa = (2) /N Bechuanaland Ghanzi Mongalatsila 31.iii.1925 J. Maurice/ /Brit. Mus. 1925-302/ /*Meria umbratica* (Turn) ♀ det 1950 C.J. Guillardmod/ BMNH; (2) /South Africa E. Cape Schilpad Laagte farm (15.4 km SW Kirkwood) 33°31.653'S 22°22.620'E 19-26 feb 2001 S. Van Noort Yellow pan trap VB01-AIT-Y30 Valley bushveld (goat trashed)/ /SAM-HYM A021103/ SAM(1)-/SAM-HYM A021411/ MZUF(1); (1) /Sout Africa E. Cape Mannetije farm (31.9 km 262° W Kirkwood) 33°32.724'S 25°08.795'E 10-17 Feb 2001 S.Van Noort Yellow pan trap VB01-R3T-Y125 Valley bushveld (goat trashed)/ /SAM-HYM A021104/

♂

Botswana = (1) /Botswana (B4) Ghanzi 13-14.iv.1972/ /Southern Africa Exped. 1972-I/ BMNH; (1) /Botswana (B8) L. Ngami NE Sehithwa 15-16.IV.1972/ /Southern African Exp. B.M. 1972-1/ MZUF; (1) /R.S.A. west Cape Riviersonderend 20.11.2002 leg. Marek Halada/ OLML

South Africa = (2) /SW Africa (W54) Regenstein 15mls SSW Windhoek 9.iv.1972/ /Southern Africa Exped. 1972-I/ BMNH; (1) /SW Africa (W48) Kombat 1-6.iv.1972/ /Southern Africa Exped. 1972-I/ BMNH

Note. The male here ascribe to *M.umbratica* just on the ground of similar distribution area and labels do not show significant differences from the type of *M. impetuosa*, name which should be abandoned if this identity would be confirmed. Nevertheless the huge gap between the relative areas and the lack hitherto of any record of the female *M.umbratica* north of Botswana force to use a conservative criterion.

Meria basutorum (Turner, 1913)

Myzine basutorum: TURNER (1913: 736 ♂)

Meria basutorum: BONI BARTALUCCI (2009: 1840, ♀ & ♂)

♀ (Fig. 23)

South Africa = (1) /Cape Province Little Karroo 38 m E of Ceres 17-25.xi.1924 14-27.xi.1928/ /S.Africa R.E. Turner Brit. Mus 1924-518/ BMNH; (1) /Cape Province Matjiesfontein 25-30.x.1928/ /S. Africa R.E. Turner Brit. Mus 1928-499/ BMNH; (1) /Cape Province Matjiesfontein 14-27.xi.1928/ /S. Africa R.E. Turner Brit. Mus 1928-542/ BMNH; (9) /South Africa E. Cape Schilpad Laagte farm (14.7 km 226° SW Kirkwood) 33°31.653'S 25°22.620'E/ /9-16 Feb 2001 S. Van Noort yellow pan trap VB01-A1N-Y37 Valley bushveld (not trashed)/ /*Tiphiidae*: *Myzininae Meria* sp A ♀ det. FW Gess2003/ [/SAM HYM A021101, A021406, A021407, (2) A021408, A021410, A021409/ SAM(7) - /SAM HYM A021101, A021102/ MZUF(2)]; (4) / /South Africa E. Cape Blaauwe Kraas farm (12.8 km 216° SW Kirkwood 33°30.747'S 25°24.644'E/ /9-16 Feb 2001 S. Van Noort yellow pan trap VB01-A3N-Y51 Valley bushveld (not trashed)/ /*Tiphiidae*: *Myzininae Meria* sp A ♀ det. FW Gess2003/ [/SAM-HYM A021403, A021404, A021405/ SAM(3) - /A021405/ MZUF(1)]; (1) R.S.A. W Cape

Klein Karoo Groot riv. 25.X.99 Leg M. Halada/ OLML; (1) /R.S.A. W Cape Klein Karoo, Langberg Grot riv.15.2.2007 leg. Marek Halada/ OLML

Note. These females perfectly fit to the female determined by Jacot-Guillarmod (BONI BARTALUCCI 2009: 1840).

Meria luteipes Boni Bartalucci, 2005

Meria luteipes: BONI BARTALUCCI (2005: 1086-1087)

♀

Madagascar = (1) /Bekily Madag. XII.33 A. Seyrig/ MZUF

Meria dissimilis Boni Bartalucci, 2009

Meria dissimilis: BONI BARTALUCCI (2009: 1830-1831)

♀

South Africa = (1) /Cape Province Matjiesfontein 14-27.xi.1928/ /S. Africa R.E. Turner Brit. Mus 1928-542/ MZUF

Meria erythraea Boni Bartalucci, 2009

Meria erythraea: BONI BARTALUCCI (2009: 1833-1834)

♂

Erythraea = (2) /Colonia Eritrea E. Africa R.E. Turner 1910-403/ /*Meria* sp. ?/ BMNH; (1) /Asmara Eritrea/ Turner Coll. 1909-49/ BMNH

Meria trachelopsila Boni Bartalucci, 2009

Meria trachelopsila: BONI BARTALUCCI (2009: 1835-1836, Figs 77-84)

♂

Namibia = (1) /SW Africa 19°14'S 20°14'/ /CO Handley jr XI.1952/ USNM

Meria leucospila Boni Bartalucci, 2009

Meria leucospila: BONI BARTALUCCI (2009: 1836)

♂

South Africa = (1) /R.S.A. W Cape 20 km N Cistrusdal 20.X.1999 leg. M. Halada/ OLML

Meria dasymetopa Boni Bartalucci, 2009

Meria dasymetopa: BONI BARTALUCCI (2009: 1837-1838, Figs 103-110)

♂

South Africa = (1) /Mamathes Basutoland Feb. 17.1.1949 J.C. Bradley/ MZUF; (1) /Hensley's Dam Leribe Dist. Basutoland feb. 21. 1949 J.C. Bradley/ CUIC

Meria masaica Boni Bartalucci, 2009

Meria masaica: BONI BARTALUCCI (2009: 1838)

♂

Kenya = (10) /Kenya Laikipia Mpala Res. Centre GR 0017N 0365E Coll. P. Lenguya/ /Tiphidae *Meria/Mesa* sp. Det. K. Baldock 2005/ /K. Baldock & G. Stone coll. BMNH(E) 2008-82/ BMNH [(3) /Net at *Acacia etbaica* (sic!) flowers 08.III.2004 Airstrip 0402/; (1) /Net at *Acacia tortilis* flowers 11.II.2004 Main gate 0434/; (1) /Net at *Acacia brevispica* flowersw 14:54 28.vii.2004 Nanjo Glade 1247/; (1) /Net at *Acacia brevispica* flowersw 11:58 29.vii.2004 Nanjo Glade 1247/; (1) /Net at *Acacia etbaica* (sic!) flowers 14:20 17.viii.2004 pumphouse 1297/; (1) /Net at *Acacia etbaica* (sic!) flowers 10:38 2.ix.2004 MRC main gate 1337/; (1) /Net at *Acacia etbaica* (sic!) flowers 12:10 3.XII.2004 Airstrip/; (1) /Net at *Acacia etbaica* (sic!) flowers 09:54 06.I.2005 Airstrip/]

Note. These specimens lack of any ferruginous colour, which is present in the holotype.

Myzinella swalei (Turner, 1911)

Myzine swalei: TURNER (1911: 616)

Myzinella swalei: GORBATOVSKY (1981: 381)

♀

Namibia = (1) /Gochenagas 218 Windhoek 22°49'S 17°12'E 17 Sept.-20 = ct. 1981 Preserv. Traps M.-L. Penrith/ /Namibian National Insect Collection National Museum P.O. Box 1203 Windhoek, Namibia/; (1) /Mamili Nat. Park 18°22'S 23°43'E 27.XI-6..XII.1991 E. Marais Pres. Pitf. Traps burnt floodplain/ MZUF

♂

Angola = (2) /Angola (A15) R. Giraul 10 mls NE Mocamedes 27-29.ii.1972/ /Southern African Exp. B.M. 1972-1/ BMNH

Namibia = (1) /S.W. Africa (30) Ameib Farm 19 mls NW Karibib 31.I-2.II.1972/ BMNH; (2) /Namibia West caprivi Pk. Kwango river Susuwe 17°45'37S 23°20'55E 28.ix-02.x.1998 A.H. Kirk-Spriggs malaise trap dry woodland/ /Namibian National Insect Collection National Museum P.O. Box 1203 Windhoek, Namibia/

South Africa = (1) /Cape Provinc Little Karroo 38 m. E of Ceres 17-25.xi.1924/ /S. Africa R.E. Turner Brit. Mus. 1924-518/ BMNH; (3) /Cape Town Milnerton Jan. 1926/ /S. Africa R.E. Turner Brit. Mus. 1926-119/ BMNH; (11) /Cape Town Milnerton Feb. 1926/ /S. Africa R.E. Turner Brit. Mus. 1926-119/ BMNH; (1) /Cape Province Matjesfontein 1-6.xi.1928/ /S. Africa R.E. Turner Brit. Mus. 1928-515/ BMNH; (1) /Cape Province Matjesfontein 7-13.xi.1928/ /S. Africa R.E. Turner Brit. Mus. 1928-522/ BMNH; (1) /Cape Province Matjesfontein 14-27.xi.1928/ /S. Africa R.E. Turner Brit. Mus. 1928-542/ BMNH; (2) /Cape Province Prince Albert Rd. Nov. 1931/ /S. Africa R.E. Turner Brit. Mus. 1931-564/ BMNH; (1) /S. Africa (16) Hester Malan 10 mls. E Springbok 7-8.i.1972/ /Southern African Exp. B.M. 1972-1/ BMNH; (4) /R.S.A. W. Cape 40km S Lamberts bay 30.X.1999 leg. Marek Halada/ OLML; (1) /R.S.A. W Cape Lamberts bay coast 29.X.1999 leg. Marek Halada/ OLML; (1) /R.S.A. northern capèc SW pof Springbok Buffels wadi 4.XI:1999 leg. M. Halada/ OLML

Note. Females here recorded show the typical features of the genus (very close **ol** to the vertex in frontal aspect with relative distance shorter than their diameter, well detectable gradulus only on 2nd **Ter** and absent on 3rd **Ter**, far distanced lateral areas on 2nd to 5th **Ter**), but they have fused **Tsa** and prostigma not longer than scape.

Macromeria klugii (Westwood, 1835)

Meria klugii: WESTWOOD (1835: 53)

Macromeria klugii: BONI BARTALUCCI (2007: 1284-1285)

♀

South Africa = (1) /South Africa Western Cape Knersvlakte, Farm Kaap se Drif. S 31°26'01", E 18°47'34" 23-9.1999 M. Kuhlmann leg/ /*Mesa sp.-det.* T. Osten/ BMNH

♂

South Africa = (1) /Kamieskroom Namaqualand/ /SAM-HYM A002459/

Macromeria semirufa (Gerstaecker, 1858)

Meria (Pseudomeria) semirufa: GERSTAECKER (1858: 512)

Macromeria semirufa: BONI BARTALUCCI (2007:1285-1286)

♀

Mozambique = (1) /Lour. Marquez Port E. Africa Herman Junod/ CUIC

Namibia = (1) /S.W. Africa (31) Okahandja 2-4.II.1972/ /Southern African Exp. B.M. 1972-1/ BMNH

South Africa = (1) /RSA OFS Warrentoa XI.2000/ OLML

Zimbabwe = (1) /Zimbabwe centr. Mvuma route Gutu Chatsworth 16.12.1998 leg. Snižek/ OLML; (6) /19°55'30" E GPS 1100 m/ /W Zimbabwe 60 km N of Bulawayo Maraposa rd 1.i.1999 M. Snižek leg/ OLML

♂

Namibia = (1) /S.W. Africa (31) Okahandja 2-4.II.1972/ /Southern African Exp. B.M. 1972-1/ BMNH; (1) /Namibia Distr. Kavango I Rundu 15-20 km E der Stadt 17°56'20" S 19°55'30" E 13.02.1994 leg. H. & R. Rausch 94-21/ OLML

Zimbabwe = (2) /W Zimbabwe 60 km N of Bulawayo Maraposa rd 1.i.1999 M. Snižek leg/ OLML

Macromeria infradentata (Turner, 1913)

Myzine infradentata: TURNER (1913: 728-729)

Macromeria infradentata: BONI BARTALUCCI (2007:1286)

♂

Namibia = (3) /Namibia Distr. Kavango I Rundu 15-20 km E der Stadt 17°56'20" S 19°55'30" E 13.02.1994 leg. H. & R. Rausch 94-21/ OLML(2)-MZUF(1)

Meriodes ceresensis (Turner, 1926)

Myzine ceresensis: TURNER (1926: 109-110)

Meriodes ceresensis: BONI BARTALUCCI (2007: 1279-1280)

♂

South Africa = (15) /South Africa/ /Cape Town Jan-Apr 1915/ /J.C. Bridwell collector/ USNM(12)-MZUF(3)

Zezeida stigma (Turner, 1912)

Myzine stigma: TURNER (1912: 699-700)

Zezeida stigma: BONI BARTALUCCI (2007: 1289)

♂

South Africa = (1) /Murraysburg Dis. C.P. – Museum staff Mar. 1931/ /SAM-HYM A022592/ MZUF

Allomeria pinguis (Turner, 1916)

Myzine pinguis: TURNER (1916: 458-459)

Allomeria pinguis: BONI BARTALUCCI (2007: 1287-1288, Figs 101-110)

♂

Zimbabwe = (1) /Gweru Nalatale Ruins 7.xii.1998 M. Snižek leg/ MZUF

Notomeria mutilloides (Turner, 1913)

Braunsomeria mutilloides: TURNER (1913: 721-722)

Notomeria mutilloides: BONI BARTALUCCI (2011: 379, Figs 67-68)

♀

Zimbabwe = (1) /ex stomach control Umtali S.Rhodesia Nat. Museum Rhodesia/ /SAM-HYM A022591/

♂

Zimbabwe = (1) /Rhodesia Victoria falls Natl. Park IV.3-6.1968 Paul Spengler/ MZUF

Note. Fig. 42bis. Very close in habitus to *N. constrictiventris* (TURNER, 1912), from which is well known by the more slender flagellum, more globular 1st tergum, the much higher gradulus at the base of terga, deeper notch of 7th tergum, more slender aedeagus. This coupling has been performed just upon the base of geographical considerations.

Discussion

The most striking feature about distribution areas of the taxa here dealt with is the complete segregation between areas north of wet equatorial belt and areas south of it; none of the Austral taxa lodges in the former and vice versa for the fewer northern taxa; the sole opposing record of *M. cingulata* from Erythraea (BONI BARTALUCCI, 2004a) has been misinterpreted in place of *M. conophora* (see under relative topic). Taxa from areas North of Equator along the Sahel belt till Erythraea and Somalia are obviously considered belonging to Afrotropical fauna, even though Afrotropical taxa cohabit there with taxa of the Palaearctic genus *Poecilotiphia* Cameron, 1902 (see BONI BARTALUCCI, 2016) and with *Meria diplochora* Boni Bartalucci, 2008, present on the Southern Arabian Peninsula too; the latter is considered pertaining to Palaearctic Region, even though it could effectively be included also into the Afrotropical fauna. Moreover the relative paucity of taxa from this area appears a bit anomalous and probably owing to a deficit of investigations. The more consistent hypothesis inferred from actually available data is that Austral Africa could be the main

dispersal centre of the genus, for the Afrotropical Region at least. Here the presence of largest number of species and the broadest degree of variability occur and indicate that the group has existed for longer time than in other areas. This hypothesis could be strengthened by the unique presence in this area of the other subtribe, Braunsomeriina Boni Bartalucci, 2004b. Compared with palaeartic members of the genus the Afrotropical taxa show an higher degree of variability about some of the main distinctive character states for the genus, namely the presence of an additional lamellar keel on the hind coxa and the particular aedeagus in some males. The lamellar extension of the keel along the fore border of the N₁ disk, present at least partially in all the palaeartic taxa, is lacking instead in the vast majority of the males of the afrotropical taxa; it is well developed only in *M. sublevis*, *M. limata*, *M. bonaespei* and present in *M. servillei*, *M. erythraea*, *M. leucospila*. Unfortunately most of taxa are known only by one sex since their association actually can not be accomplished because of wanting data from the field. Some of the few known couplings have been performed by JACOT-GUILLARMOD in paper (1961) and in labels too. Further field investigations and deeper searching into areas hitherto poorly known (Angola, Zimbabwe, Sahel) will produce probably both new sex associations and discovery of new species.

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Received 17 November 2017

Accepted 30 March 2018

Figs 1-12. *Meria* sp. ♀ - (1): head, lateral aspect; (6): head, ventral aspect; (7): labium, ventral aspect; (8): labrum, frontal aspect. *Meria oinodes* ♀ - (2): ventral aspect; (3): labium, ventral aspect; (4): labrum, frontal aspect; (5) scape, frontal aspect. *Meria dissimilis* ♀ - (9): clypeus, FoO & PoG, ventral aspect. *Meria stenogastra* ♀ - (10): head frontal aspect. *Meria namachorites* ♀ - (11): clypeus, FoO & PoG, ventral aspect; (12): clypeus (partially) and mandible, frontal aspect.
 (1), (6): scale bar 'a' = 1 mm; (7), (8): scale bar 'a' = 0.5 mm; (2), (5): scale bar 'b' = 1 mm; (3),(4), (8): scale bar 'b' = 0.5 mm; (9): scale bar 'c' = 0.5 mm; (10), (11), (12): scale bar 'c' = 1 mm.

Figs 13-20. *Meria deiandra* ♀ - (13): lower head and mandibles, frontal aspect. *Meria namachorites* ♀ - (14): labrum, ventral aspect. *Meria stenogastra* ♀ - (15): labrum, ventral aspect. *Meria neavei* ♀ - (16): head, ventral aspect; (17): general habitus. *Meria perornata* ♀ - (18): Tsa (particular), frontal aspect; (19): head (particular), ventral aspect; (20): general habitus. (13): scale bar = 1 mm; (14), (15): scale bar = 0.5 mm; (16), (18), (19): scale bar = 0.25 mm; (17), (20): scale bar = 5 mm.

21

22

23

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Figs 21-24. *Meria sublevis* ♀ - (21): general habitus. *Meria umbratica* ♀ - (22): general habitus. *Meria basatorum* ♀ - (23): general habitus. *Meria rufinodis* ♀ - (24): general habitus. (21), (22), (23), (24): scale bar = 5 mm.

Figs 25-37. *Meria oinodes* ♂ - (25): labium, ventral aspect; (26): foretibial spur. *Meria* sp. ♂ - (27): labium, ventral aspect; (28): foretibial spur. *Meria trachelopsila* ♂ - (29): pronotum, dorsal aspect; (30): gonosquama; (31): gonosquama (with aedeagus) inner lateral aspect; (32): volsella; (33): aedeagus, ventral aspect. *Meria leucospila* ♂ - (34): pronotum, dorsal aspect; (35): gonosquama, outer lateral, ventral and inner lateral aspect, with aedeagus; (36): volsella; (37): aedeagus ventral aspect.
 (25), (26), (27), (28): scale bar = 0.5 mm; (29), (34): scale bar = 2 mm; (30), (31), (32), (33), (35), (36), (37): scale bar = 0.75 mm.

Figs 38-42 bis. *Meria discontinua* ♂ - (38): hind coxa, back aspect. *Meria masaica* ♂ - (39): gonosquama. *Meria leucospila* ♂ - (40): 2nd Tergum, dorsal aspect. *Meria lasiotera* ♂ - (41): side of 4th metamerus (particular), lateral aspect. *Meria pallidipes* ♀ - (42): propodeum, dorsal aspect. *Notomeria mutilloides* ♂ - (42 bis): habitus with particular of 4th metamerus in lateral aspect.

(38), (39), (41): scale bar = 0.5 mm; (40), (42): scale bar = 1 mm; (42 bis): scale bar = 5 mm.

Figs 43-50. *Meria aequatorialis* ♂ - (43): head, dorsal aspect; (44): head frontal aspect; (45): palpi; (46): pronotum, dorsal aspect; (47): 7th tergum, dorsal aspect; (48): gonosquama; (49): volsella; (50): aedeagus. (43): scale bar = 2 mm; (44), (46), (47): scale bar = 1 mm; (45), (48), (49), (50): scale bar = 0.5 mm.

Figs 51-58. *Meria conophora* ♂ - (51): head, dorsal aspect; (52): head, frontal aspect; (53): pronotum, dorsal aspect; (54): pronotum, lateral aspect; (55): 7th tergum, dorsal aspect; (56): gonosquama; (57): volsella; (58): aedeagus.
(51), (54): scale bar = 2 mm; (52), (53), (55): scale bar = 1 mm; (56), (57), (58): scale bar = 0.5 mm.

Figs 59-65. *Meria hermonensis* ♂ - (59): head, dorsal aspect; (60): head, frontal aspect; (61): pronotum, dorsal aspect; (61 bis): pronotum, lateral aspect; (62): 7th tergum, dorsal aspect; (63): gonosquama, ventral and inner lateral aspect; (64): volsella; (65): aedeagus.
(59): scale bar = 2 mm; (60), (61), (61 bis), (62): scale bar = 1 mm; (63), (64), (65): scale bar = 0.5 mm.

Figs 66-74. *Meria eterodira* ♂ - (66): general habitus; (67): head, dorsal aspect; (68): head, frontal aspect; (69): pronotum, dorsal aspect; (70): pronotum, lateral aspect; (71): 7th tergum, dorsal aspect (drawing and photo); (72): gonosquama; (73): volsella; (74): aedeagus.
(66): scale bar = 2.5 mm; (67), (68): scale bar = 1 mm; (69), (70), (71), (72), (73), (74): scale bar = 0.5 mm.

Figs 75-84. *Meria namibensis* ♂ - (75): head, dorsal aspect; (76): head, frontal aspect; (77): flagellum, dorsal aspect; (78): head (particular), ventral aspect; (79): pronotum, dorsal aspect; (80): pronotum, lateral aspect; (81): 7th tergum, dorsal aspect; (82): gonosquama; (83): volsella; (84): aedeagus.
(75), (76), (77): scale bar = 2 mm; (79), (80), (81): scale bar = 1 mm; (78), (82), (83), (84): scale bar = 0.5 mm.

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Figs 85-87. *Meria noorti* ♀ - (85): general habitus; (86): head, frontal aspect. *Meria dissimilis* ♀ - (87): general habitus.

(85), (87): scale bar = 2.5 mm; (86): scale bar = 1 mm.

Figs 88-95. *Meria ordinaria* ♀ - (88): general habitus; (89): head, frontal aspect; (90): head, ventral aspect; (91): palpi; (92): mesosoma, dorsal aspect; (93): fore wing, particular; (94): basal hind tarsomerus; (95): basal metameri, dorsal aspect.
(88): scale bar = 2.5 mm; (89), (92), (95): scale bar = 1 mm; (90), (91), (93), (94): scale bar = 0.5 mm.

Figs 96-105. *Meria ornativentris* ♂ - (96): head, frontal aspect; (97): clypeus, ventral edge; (98): pronotum, dorsal aspect; (99): pronotum, lateral aspect; (100): metasoma, dorsal aspect; (101): 7th tergum, dorsal aspect; (102): 7th tergum, lateral aspect; (103): gonosquama, outer lateral and ventral aspects; (104): volsella; (105): aedeagus. (100): scale bar = 3 mm; (96), (98), (99): scale bar = 2 mm; (101), (102): scale bar = 1 mm; (97), (103), (104), (105): scale bar = 0.5 mm.

Figs 106-113. *Meria peripatetica* ♀ - (106): general habitus; (107): head, frontal aspect; (108): head, ventral aspect; (109): palpi; (110): mesosoma, dorsal aspect; (111): fore wing; (112): hind wing; (113): hind tarsomerus. (106): scale bar = 2 mm; (107), (110): scale bar = 1 mm; (108), (109), (111), (112), (113): scale bar = 0.5 mm.

Figs 114-121. *Meria shabeella* ♂ - (114): head, dorsal aspect; (115): head, frontal aspect; (116): palpi; (117): pronotum, dorsal aspect; (118): 7th tergum, dorsal aspect; (119): gonosquama, ventral and outer lateral aspect; (120): voisella; (121): aedeagus. (114), (115), (117): scale bar = 1 mm; (116), (118), (119), (120), (121): scale bar = 0.5 mm.

Figs 122-130. *Meria mhaladai* ♂ - (122): head, dorsal aspect; (123): head, frontal aspect; (124): 7th flagellomeres, anteroventral aspect; (125): pronotum, dorsal aspect; (126): pronotum, lateral aspect; (127): 7th tergum, dorsal aspect; (128): gonosquama; (129): volsella; (130): aedeagus.
(122), (123), (125), (126): scale bar = 1 mm; (127), (128), (129), (130): scale bar = 0.5 mm.

Figs 131-141. *Poecilotiphia australis* ♀ - (131): head, dorsal aspect; (132): head, frontal aspect; (133): head, lateral aspect; (134): head, ventral aspect; (135): scape and basal flagellomeres in dorsal aspect; (136): scape, frontal aspect; (137): palpi; (138): mesosoma, dorsal aspect; (139): pronotum, lateral aspect; (140): fore wing, particular; (141): fore tibial spur.
 (131), (132), (133), (134), (136), (138), (139): scale bar = 1 mm; (135), (137), (140), (141): scale bar = 0.5 mm.

Figs 142-151. *Poecilotiphia idioptera* ♀ - (142): head, dorsal aspect; (143): head frontal aspect; (144): head, ventral spect; (145): scape, dorsal aspect; (146): scape, frontal aspect; (147): palpi; (148): mesosoma, dorsal aspect; (149): fore wing, particular; (150): fore tibial spur; (151): last hind tarsomeri. (142), (148): scale bar = 2 mm; (143), (144), (146): scale bar = 1 mm; (145), (147), (149), (150), (151): scale bar = 9.5 mm.

Figs 152-162. *Meriodes laticeps* ♂ - (152): general habitus; (153): head, dorsal aspect; (154): head, frontal aspect; (155): flagellum; (156): pronotum, dorsal aspect; (157): fore tibia spur; (158): 7th tergum, dorsal aspect; (159): 7th tergum, lateral aspect; (160): gonosquama; (161): volsella; (162): aedeagus, ventral and lateral aspect. (152): scale bar = 5 mm; (155): scale bar = 2 mm; (153), (154), (156), (159): scale bar = 12 mm; (157), (158), (160), (161), (162): scale bar = 0.5 mm.